

РИТМ
УГЛЕРОДА

HIT HUMIC
2025 INNOVATIVE
TECHNOLOGIES

Humic substances and plant raw materials in the context of a closed-loop economy

**Tenth International Conference of the CIS IHSS
on Humic Innovative Technologies**

**September 25-27, 2025
Syktyvkar, Russia**

**International Humic Substances Society,
Chapter of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS)
Federal Research Centre "Komi Science Centre of the Ural
Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences"
Institute of Biology of Komi Science Centre of the Ural Branch
of the Russian Academy of Sciences
RITM Carbon Consortium
Isaev Centre for Forest Ecology and Productivity
of the Russian Academy of Sciences**

Book of abstracts

**Tenth International Conference of the CIS IHSS
on Humic Innovative Technologies**

Humic substances and plant raw materials in the context of a closed-loop economy

September 25-27, 2025

Syktyvkar, Russia

**Syktyvkar, Russia
IB FRC Komi SC UB RAS
2025**

УДК 547:631.417:615.32
ББК 24.73:41.8
Н 91

Edited by Dr. Evgeny D. Lodygin

Н 91 **Humic substances and plant raw materials in the context of a closed-loop economy** : book of abstracts : Tenth International Conference of the CIS IHSS on Humic Innovative Technologies : September 25–27, 2025, Syktyvkar, Russia. – Syktyvkar : IB FRC Komi SC UB RAS, 2025. – 69 p.

ISBN 978-5-6053974-2-7 (Electronic book)

This book contains abstracts of reports from the Tenth International Conference of the CIS IHSS on Humic Innovative Technologies “Humic substances and plant raw materials in the context of a closed-loop economy”. The conference covers a wide range of topics, from the theoretical foundations of the molecular analysis of humic substances and plant raw materials using modern analytical methods, to new applications of artificial humification products and the processing of plant biopolymers within the bioeconomy and circular economy. It also discusses the role of humic substances and soil organic matter components in the carbon cycle in terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. Particular attention is paid to the use of humic preparations and plant raw materials in nature conservation and biomedical technologies. **Abstracts published in the author's edition.**

УДК 547:631.417:615.32
ББК 24.73:41.8

ISBN 978-5-6053974-2-7 (Electronic book)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17198173

© IB FRC Komi SC UB RAS, 2025

International Program Committee

Irina V. Perminova	Co-chair of International Program Committee, Professor, Coordinator of the CIS IHSS Chapter, Department of Chemistry, Lomonosov MSU, Moscow, Russia
Evgeny D. Lodygin	Co-chair of International Program Committee, Dr. habil., Institute of Biology, Komi SC UrBr RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia
Maria V. Zykova	Coordinator of the CIS IHSS, Professor, Siberian State Medical University, Tomsk, Russia
Aleksandr V. Kuchin	Academician of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Head of Research at the Institute of Chemistry, Komi SC UrBr RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia
Natalya V. Lukina	Corresponding Member of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Director of the Isaev Centre for Forest Ecology and Productivity of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Moscow, Russia
Serafim N. Chukov	Professor, Saint-Petersburg State University, Chair of the Commission on Soil Chemistry of the Russian Soil Science Society, Saint-Petersburg, Russia
Tatyana M. Minkina	Professor, Southern Federal University, Rostov-on-Don, Russia
Marya I. Dergacheva	Professor, Institute of Soil Science and Agrochemistry SB RAS, Novosibirsk, Russia
Anna G. Zavarzina	PhD, Department of Soil Science, Lomonosov MSU, Moscow, Russia
Gulnora T. Djalilova	Professor, National University of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, Uzbekistan
Dmitriy A. Bushnev	Corresponding Member of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Yushkin Institute of Geology, Komi SC UrBr RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia

Organizing Committee

Svetlana V. Degteva	Co-chair of Organizing Committee, Corresponding Member of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Director of the Federal Research Centre 'Komi Scientific Centre of the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences', Syktyvkar, Russia
Evgeny D. Lodygin	Co-chair of Organizing Committee, Dr. habil., Institute of Biology, Komi SC UrBr RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia
Pavel A. Arzubov	Institute of Biology, Komi SC UrBr RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia
Yuliya I. Bobrova	Institute of Biology, Komi SC UrBr RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia
Nataliya N. Bondarenko	Institute of Biology, Komi SC UrBr RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia
Alexey A. Dymov	Dr. habil., Institute of Biology, Komi SC UrBr RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia
Nataliya E. Ignatova	Institute of Biology, Komi SC UrBr RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia
Elena V. Kzyurova	Institute of Biology, Komi SC UrBr RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia
Elena M3. Lapteva	PhD, Institute of Biology, Komi SC UrBr RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia
Olga A. Ostanina	Institute of Biology, Komi SC UrBr RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia
Evgeniya M. Perminova	Institute of Biology, Komi SC UrBr RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia
Olga V. Shakhtarova	Institute of Biology, Komi SC UrBr RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia
Elena V. Shamrikova	Dr. habil., Institute of Biology, Komi SC UrBr RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia
Roman S. Vasilevich	PhD, Institute of Biology, Komi SC UrBr RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia

CONTENTS

1. Modern analytical methods for studying humic substances, soil organic matter and plant raw material.....	9
Byvsheva S.M., Volkov D.S. Calibration-based assessment of molecular formula assignment accuracy in UHRMS analysis of humic substances using a flavonoid reference material.....	10
Chabina E.A., Ishwah B., Andrianova M.Ju. Optical characteristics of urban waters containing humic substances	11
Cherepanov I.S., Egorova A.I., Tarasova D.A. Study of furan derivatives formation from the carbohydrate raw material under thermal conditions using PY-MS and FTIR spectroscopy methods	12
Djalilova G., Nurullaev A. Study and modeling of soil erosion processes under artificial rainfall conditions.....	13
Gruzdev I.V. Soil organic compounds determination by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry	14
Khreptugova A.N., Gorbunov D.M., Volkov D.S., Perminova I.V. Predictive modeling of antioxidant activity in fulvic acid fractions based on HRMS and fluorescence data	15
Khreptugova A.N., Petrov K.V., Starr S., Spencer R., Semiletov I.P., Perminova I.V. Molecular composition of dissolved organic matter in the Siberian Arctic Shelf: evidence of permafrost influence from FT-ICR MS analysis	16
Kozhamuratova U.M., Kassenova Zh.M., Malgazhdarova A.B., Kazankapova M.K., Bekbosynov A., Yermagambet B.T. Study of the effectiveness of soil purification from petroleum products using humic substances.....	17
Kushnareva A.V., Bezuglova O.S. Changes in the humus composition of dark chestnut soils in the post-meliorative period.....	18
Lodygin E., Nesterov B., Alekseev I. A new approach to assessing the content of natural hydrocarbons in soils	19
Lyu-Lyan-Min E.I., Shamrikova E.V., Gruzdev I.V., Zhangurov E.V. Extraction and fractionation of lipid components of soil by chromatographic methods.....	20
Shamrikova E., Vanchikova E., Kondratenok B., Lapteva E., Kostrova S., Tumanova E., Zonova T., Lyu-Lyan-Min E., Kzyurova E., Bondarenko N. Is it possible to harmonize the SOC measurement? Results of the 1st Eurasian GLOSOLAN PT (2023/2024)	21
Vasilevich R.S., Zherebker A.Y., Kuznetsov O.L. Stabilization of soil organic matter of palsa bogs as a response to climate change in Holocene	22
Yakovleva E.V., Gabov D.N., Vasilevich R.S., Gruzdev I.V., Shchemelinina T.N., Anchugova E.M., Gunderina E.D. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and phenanthrene derivatives in long-term stored bark and wood waste	23
2. The role of humic substances and components of soil organic matter in the carbon cycle of terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems.....	24
Bondarenko N.N., Kzyurova E.V., Lapteva E.M. Organic matter of clear-cut soils	25
Dergacheva M. Current issues of Humus science	26
Dymov A.A., Kut'yavin I.N., Startsev V.V., Gorbach N.M., Severgina D.A., Pausova I.V.,	

Vachruchev L.A., Dubrovskiy Yu.A., Nechaev R.A., Arzubov P.A., Ogorodnia S.A., Osipov A.F. The impact of harvesting operation on Albic Retisols in the middle taiga of the Komi Republic.....	27
Dymov A.A., Pausova I.V., Gorbach N.M. The role of fires in the transformation of soil organic matter	28
Gorbov S.N., Skripnikov P.N., Tishchenko S.A. The dynamics of water-soluble organic matter in constructed soils of different composition	29
Kovaleva N., Sidorova I., Kovalev I. Organic matter of buried soils as a carbon depot	30
Kubik O., Shamrikova E., Deneva S., Panyukov A. Features of the organization of amino acids in the plant-soil system of marsh ecosystems	31
Kudryavtsev A.E., Vaganov E.S., Sorokin A.S. Qualitative and quantitative characteristics of organic extract from plant materials used in lentil cultivation	32
Kuznetsov M.A., Osipov A.F. Emission of CO ₂ from spruce soils at the Lyalsky test site (Komi Republic)	33
Lapteva E., Likhanova I., Skrebenkov E., Bondarenko N., Smotrina Yu., Shchanov V. Soil organic matter and carbon stocks in soils on binary sediments	34
Lasareva E.V., Parfenova A.M. Effect of the nature of humic substances and ionic strength on the stabilization of colloidal bentonite.....	35
Nekrasova O., Uchaev A. Specificity of soil humus substances at ash dumps	36
Perminova E., Lapteva E. Is there a relationship between the carbon content of microbial biomass and soil organic matter parameters in clear-cut soils of the taiga zone?	37
Petrov K.V., Khreptugova A.N., Larionov K.S., Vladimirov S.A., Pechnikova G.S., Zhurba V.S., Perminova I.V. Comparative analysis of optical data from Solzan landfill storage cards	38
Polyakov V., Abakumov E. Post-agrogenic dynamics of molecular composition of humic acids in North-West Russia	39
Zavarzina A. The role of laccase in synthesis and degradation of humic substances.....	40

3. The use of humic substances and plant raw materials in nature conservation and biomedical technologies 41

Alferova V.S., Kosolapova N.I., Nevedrov N.P. The detoxification potential of activated peat hydrosol towards cadmium ions	42
Bezuglova O., Gorovtsov A., Lychman V., Polienko E. The influence of humic preparations on soil fertility and the yield of pea (<i>Pisum sativum</i> L.)	43
Chukov S.N. Humification is a natural, nature-preserving technology that can be used in a closed-loop economy	44
Gileva D.A., Inisheva L.I., Porokhina E.V. Chemical and biological activity of peats.....	45
Karpova A.E., Skripkina.T.S. The use of humic acids and their salts to extract gallium from the fly ash of brown coal thermal power plants	46
Karpova Y.I., Igumnova A.A., Tikhonova T.V. Antioxidant activity of various fractions of humic substances in cosmetic compositions	47
Kocheva L.S., Karmanov A.P., Raskosha O.V. Lignins as promising plant polymers for biomedical applications	48

Kriuchkova D.S., Zhirkova A.M., Shestakov K.D., Larionov K.S., Volkov D.S., Konstantinov A.I., Perminova I.V. Injection fluids based on humic acid-3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane complexes for immobilization of heavy metals	49
Kuzmin D.V., Burtsev I.N., Brovarova O.V. Investigation of the properties of humic acids of coal sludge from the Inta Mining and Processing Plant	50
Minkina T.M., Bauer T.V. Processing of plant raw materials using closed-loop technologies to enhance soil quality and safety	51
Nazarov A.M., Chetverikov S.P., Davletshin T.K. Fuel oil contaminated ecosystems treatment using microbiological preparation in combination with dispersants based on humic substances and natural raw materials.....	52
Poloskov A.I., Tovpeko D.V., Yu Z., Larionov K.S., Soloviev D.A., Mitiukov A.S., Alexander-Sinclair E., Perminova I.V., Glushakov R.I. Study of some biological effects of humic substances.....	53
Rubtsova S.A., Chukicheva I.Yu., Hurshkainen T.V., Udoratina E.V., Kutchin A.V. Development and achievements of the scientific school «Scientific Fundamentals of Plant Materials Chemistry and Technology»	54
Shunkova D.M., Pilguk G., Tagirov T.R., Karpova M.R., Zyкова M.V. Antifungal effect of silver-containing bionanomaterials based on humic ligands	55
Ushakova K.A., Badun G.A., Chernysheva M.G., Farsobina O.A., Zhirkova A.M., Perminova I.V. Synthesis of iron(III)-humic substances complexes of different lipophilicity profile with a use of alcohol precipitation	56
Zhirkova A.M., Lakienko G.P., Kriuchkova D.S., Gadzhibagomedov R.A., Rajabzoda P.A., Perminova I.V. Humic substances-assisted immobilization of magentite onto sawdust increases surface area and copper bonding of the sorbent.....	57
Zhurba V.S., Yakimenko O.S. Effect of C-based soil conditioners on the composition and properties of soil organic matter	58
4. The role of humic substances and plant biopolymers in the context of the bioeconomy.....	59
Dinu M. Biospheric functions of humic substances – geochemical barriers and nature-like technologies.....	60
Efanov M.V., Konshin V.V. New methods of chemical functionalization of peat	61
Kondratiev V.M. The use of LLC Lignohumat preparations containing humic substances in agriculture.....	62
Martynov V.V., Shchemelinina T.N., Anchugova E.M., Perestoronniy D.V., Molodkina N.R. The principle of cascade utilization in the processing of coffee silverskin	63
Perminova I.V. Evolutionary chemistry of carbon as a molecular basis for ecoadaptive technologies.....	64
Advertisement	65

1. Modern analytical methods for studying humic substances, soil organic matter and plant raw material

Calibration-based assessment of molecular formula assignment accuracy in UHRMS analysis of humic substances using a flavonoid reference material

Byvsheva S.M.¹, Volkov D.S.¹

¹Chemistry Department, M.V. Lomonosov Moscow State University, Moscow, Russia,
sophia.byvsheva@gmail.com

Keywords: high-resolution mass-spectrometry, natural organic matter, accuracy, internal calibration
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17318884

The primary method for analyzing the molecular composition of natural organic matter (NOM) is high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS). Obtaining accurate and reproducible data on the molecular composition of NOM samples is essential for addressing environmental chemistry problems. Calibration is a key step in achieving high mass accuracy. Internal calibration can be performed using the detection of known compounds within the sample. However, due to the limited information available on compounds present in NOM, calibration solutions can be added and mixed with the sample prior to analysis.

Commercially available reference materials (RM) of natural compounds were used as external standards and added to Suwannee River fulvic acid (SRFA) solutions. The RM included flavonoids, which are common in nature and share molecular formulas with ions found in humic substances (HS). Three types of spectra were recorded: (i) without internal calibration, (ii) with internal calibration using the mass 212.075074, corresponding to *N*-butylbenzenesulfonamide (a plasticizer from tubing used in gas transfer to the mass spectrometer), and (iii) with internal calibration using ions from a standard flavonoid solution added to SRFA. In total, 20 spectra were obtained, with two replicates for each spectrum type, collected at equal time intervals. Both approaches to internal calibration (Figure 1, A and B) resulted in improved accuracy compared to spectra recorded without internal calibration (Figure 1, C). For single-ion calibration, a decrease in reproducibility was observed for ions with high *m/z* values, whereas for calibration with 10 ions, reproducibility was consistent across the entire *m/z* range, with 3σ not exceeding 0.5 ppm. Analysis of Shewhart charts and the calculation of metrological characteristics for 21 analyte ions confirmed the advantages of using internal calibration with 10 ions.

Figure 1. Mass accuracy plots for 21 analytical ions (black line – μ (mean mass error), grey line – 3σ and -3σ (σ – standard deviation): A - without internal calibration, B - with internal calibration using one mass, C - with internal calibration using 10 masses, corresponding to ions present in a standard solution of flavonoids added to SRFA.

Acknowledgements. The work was supported by the Russian Science Foundation, project number 21-73-20202.

Optical characteristics of urban waters containing humic substances

Chabina E.A.¹, Ishwah B.¹, Andrianova M.Ju.¹

¹Peter the Great St.Petersburg Polytechnic University, St.Petersburg, Russia,
andrianova_myu@spbstu.ru

Keywords: optical density, fluorescence, surface water, pollution, NOM
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17321601

The Murinsky creek is a tributary of the river Okhta, which is the most polluted river in Saint-Petersburg. Water samples of the Murinsky creek were studied to suggest optical parameters for location of wastewater outlets, polluting the urban flow. The following indicators (variables) of water were measured: concentrations of main ions, electric conductivity (EC), optical density at 254 nm (D_{254}), fluorescence intensity in UV region at certain excitation and emission wavelengths ($I_{ex,em}$), total organic carbon (TOC), inorganic carbon (IC), total nitrogen (TN).

Principal component analysis found 6 significant principal components (PC). Three of them formed 87% of data dispersion. According to the loadings PC1 could be responsible for wastewater pollution. PC 1 explains 44% of data dispersion. Variables have high and moderate positive loadings (0.64...0.87) on PC1 for main ions concentrations, EC and TN, and also protein-like fluorescence (emission at 300-350 nm). This is typical for pollution with municipal wastewater. D_{254} has negative loading on PC1 (-0.64), TOC and humic-like fluorescence (emission at 420 nm) has insignificant negative loadings (-0.02...-0.22). This can be explained by high natural background formed by humic substances in unpolluted creek water, which does not allow wastewater to increase TOC and humic-like fluorescence after mixing with natural water.

PC2 has negative loadings (-0.14...-0.50) for EC and main ions concentrations and positive loadings for TN, D_{254} , protein-like and humic-like fluorescence (0.13...0.69). PC2 could also be responsible for organic components of wastewater.

PC3 has positive loadings on EC, TOC, D_{254} , humic-like fluorescence (0.34...0.64), negative loading for TN and protein-like fluorescence (-0.08...-0.39). Maybe PC 3 is responsible for natural background variations, explained by humic substances.

These results of PC analysis have some common features with results for river Okhta [1]. Both investigations allow to suggest the most suitable combination of variables as indicators of water pollution: EC and $I_{230,350}$.

References

1. Chabina E.A., Andrianova M.Ju. Fluorometricheskij monitoring zagraznenij rechnoj vody // Bidiagnostica sostojanija prirodnykh i pripidno-technogennyh system: Materials of XXII All-Russian scientific and practical conference with international participation, Kirov, November 18–19, 2024. – Kirov: Vyatka state university, 2024. – pp. 32-36. – EDN FPWCSO.

Study of furan derivatives formation from the carbohydrate raw material under thermal conditions using PY-MS and FTIR spectroscopy methods

Cherepanov I.S.¹, Egorova A.I.¹, Tarasova D.A.¹

¹Udmurt State University, Izhevsk, Russia, cherchem@mail.ru

Keywords: carbohydrates, furan, thermodestruction, mechanism, spectroscopy

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17321919

The results of furan structural fragment's formation in *D*-maltose (as model carbohydrate system) thermodestruction products study are presented. Using derivative IR Fourier transform spectroscopy and pyrolysis-mass spectrometry (PY-MS) methods It has been shown that in processes of alkaline cleavage and dry caramelization of the initial carbohydrate the polymeric structures, containing furan heterocycles of varying substitution degree, form as a result of intramolecular condensations.

Formation of furan derivatives from carbohydrate may be presented as scheme Figure 1, **A**, illustrating intramolecular activation by the attack of O(C₂)-atom on the anomeric C₁-centre [1]. Cleavage of glycoside bond provides the monosaccharides and furfural (peaks at *m/z* = 68, 82, 96 in PY-MS spectra), further condensations lead to polymeric products, which structure depends on reaction conditions and our earlier investigation assume formation of α - and β -furan humic-like systems [2].

Figure 1. **A**, Proposed furfural formation mechanism; **B**, second derivative FTIR-spectra of solid phases: 1. – maltose alkaline cleavage products; 2. – maltose dry thermodestruction products; 3. – alkaline cleavage products after dry thermodestruction.

Analysis of 3150-3100 cm⁻¹ FTIR spectral area of solid phases of various maltose thermodestruction products allows to estimate furan cycles substitution degree [2]. Second derivative FTIR spectra (Figure 1, **B**) show difference between α/β -[C-H] content in various polymeric furans: alkaline cleavage products (intensive doublet at 3109 and 3122 cm⁻¹ in spectrum 1) contain significant part of non-substituted rings (free =C-H bonds), as soon as dry thermodestruction solid phases of initial disaccharide and its alkaline cleavage products (spectra 2 and 3) are more condensed (no sharp signals). It is also postulated, that the [=C _{α} -H]-fragments react by the electrophilic substitution mechanism, but the [=C _{β} -H]-centers transform via oxidative condensation pathway. These experimental facts are in agreement with the literature data obtained [1] and may be used in biotechnologies, perspective as a synthetic platform for biomass transformation to heterocyclic compounds.

References

1. Maliekkal V. et al. Activation of cellulose via cooperative hydroxyl-catalyzed transglycosilation of glycosidic bonds. *ACS Catal.* 2019, 9, 1943–1955.
2. Cherepanov I.S. Carbonization products in *D*-glucose-*p*-toluidin system as sorbents of carbohydrate caramels from aqueous solutions. *IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Envir. Sci.* 2019, 315(6), 062001.

Study and modeling of soil erosion processes under artificial rainfall conditions

Djalilova G.¹, Nurullaev A.²

¹National University of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, Uzbekistan, jalilova.gulnora.2024@gmail.com

²Termez State University of Engineering and Agrotechnologies, Surkhandarya, Uzbekistan, nurullayevazamxon@gmail.com

Keywords: soil erosion, artificial rainfall, laboratory model, slope angle, rainfall intensity, soil washing

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17322066

Soil erosion on agricultural lands leads to reduced productivity and intensification of degradation processes. Therefore, modeling soil washing and identifying its main factors are of significant scientific and practical importance. In this study, a special laboratory device was developed to investigate erosion processes under artificial rainfall conditions in different soil types, and an authorship certificate was obtained. Methodologically, the device allows for water supply from a 200-liter reservoir to rainfall sprayers, artificial setting of slope angles (5°, 10°, 15°, 20°), and measurement of the washed soil mass using an electronic balance and filter paper.

The experiments used 48 soil monoliths (dark gray, mountain brown carbonate, typical, and leached soils). Rainfall parameters were set at intensities of 2–4 mm/min with a duration of 20 minutes.

The results showed that slope angle and rainfall intensity are the main determinants of soil washing. For example, in dark gray soils at an intensity of 2 mm/min and a 5° slope, soil washing amounted to 0.3982 t/ha, whereas at a 20° slope this increased to 1.4089 t/ha. When rainfall intensity was 4 mm/min at a 20° slope, washing reached 1.7705 t/ha. Accordingly, soil erosion processes were found to intensify proportionally with increasing slope. Across different soil types, erosion levels varied significantly: mountain brown carbonate soils showed higher washing, while leached soils exhibited relatively lower rates.

Raindrop diameter (0.2–4.5 mm) also had varying effects on erosion processes: drops in the 1.5–3.0 mm range caused soil aggregate breakdown, decreased permeability, and formation of compacted crusts. As a result, soil water infiltration decreased and the mass of the washed layer increased sharply.

In conclusion, the artificial rainfall method is an effective model for studying soil erosion processes under laboratory conditions, and the obtained data serve as a basis for developing scientifically grounded recommendations on soil protection. Such studies are of great importance for sustainable use of water resources and maintaining the productivity of agricultural lands.

References

1. Nurullaev A.K., Djalilova Influence of slope elements on the development of soil erosion in the mountainous regions of Uzbekistan // Bulletin of Agricultural Science of Uzbekistan. 2023. No. 4 (10). – P. 27–32.
2. Djalilova G.T., Nurullaev A.K. Assessment of erosion processes in mountainous areas using artificial rainfall // Ecological Bulletin of the North Caucasus. 2025. Vol. 21. No. 2.-P. 165-173.

Soil organic compounds determination by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry

Gruzdev I.V.

Institute of Biology Komi SC UrD RAS, Syktyvkar, Russian Federation, gruzdev@ib.komisc.ru

Keywords: lipid components, extraction, fractionation, derivatization, gas chromatography, gas chromatography/mass spectrometry

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17322188

Soil is a heterogeneous system of great structural and functional complexity that acts as a regulatory center for numerous ecosystem processes. Soil organic matter is a complex mixture of biological material derived from a variety of sources, including microorganisms, plants, fungi, and animals. These materials undergo a series of degradation and transformation processes, resulting in a heterogeneous mixture of compounds that play a vital role in soil formation and functioning.

Extraction with organic solvents is used to isolate a lipid fraction containing hydrophobic organic compounds from soil. The composition of this fraction varies from complex esterified structures such as phospholipids, glycolipids, and sphingolipids to simpler molecules such as aliphatic acids, alcohols, aldehydes, and ketones [1].

Basic methodological approaches for determining organic compounds in soils typically involve several sequential steps: extraction, fractionation, chemical modification, identification, and quantitative analysis using chromatographic methods [2].

The classic method for extracting lipid components from soil is the Soxhlet method, but its use is complicated by several drawbacks, including the lengthy extraction process, high solvent consumption, and the potential for distortion of the qualitative and quantitative composition of the sample. Some of these problems can be solved using modern extraction methods, including accelerated solvent extraction (ASE). The use of the ASE method allows for automation and significant acceleration of the extraction of organic compounds from solid matrices, as well as minimizing the likelihood of distortion of the sample's component composition.

The complexity and multicomponent composition of the resulting soil extracts requires the use of chromatograph mass spectrometry for their analysis. However, even in this case, prior to instrumental analysis, preliminary fractionation of the target components by adsorption chromatography is necessary. Chemical modification methods also improve the reliability of qualitative and quantitative analysis of soil organic compounds. Changing the chemical nature of the analyzed compounds improves the stability of the resulting analytical forms, as well as the selectivity and sensitivity of their determination.

In the chromatograph mass spectrometry method, derivatization is used to increase the signal intensity of the molecular (characteristic) ion, as well as to increase the specificity of fragmentation of analytes, which ensures their more reliable identification.

The potential for using lipid components as marker compounds for various studies in soil science has not yet been fully explored, and therefore this area, including its analytical component, continues to actively develop.

References

1. Saini R.K., Prasad P., Shang X. Advances in Lipid Extraction Methods—A Review // *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 2021. V. 22. № 24. P. 13643. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms222413643>
2. Arteaga-Clemente G., García-González M.A., González-González M. Soil lipid analysis by chromatography: A critical review of the current state in sample preparation // *J. Chromatog. Open.* 2024. V. 6. P. 100173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcoa.2024.100173>

Predictive modeling of antioxidant activity in fulvic acid fractions based on HRMS and fluorescence data

Khreptugova A.N.¹, Gorbunov D.M.¹, Volkov D.S.¹, Perminova I.V.¹

¹Lomonosov Moscow State University, Department of Chemistry, Moscow, Russia,
khreptugova@mail.ru

Keywords: Fulvic Acids, Antioxidant Capacity, RP-HPLC Fractionation, High-Resolution Mass Spectrometry (HRMS), Condensed Tannins
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17322323

Fulvic acids (FA), a subclass of humic substances, are structurally complex organic macroligands known for their selective interactions with biological macromolecules and potential use as biostimulants. However, standardized protocols for isolating highly active FA components and quality control criteria remain underdeveloped. In this study, preparative reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) with a water/isopropanol eluent system was employed to fractionate a commercial FA product (Fulvagra, Humintech GmbH, Germany). Sixteen fractions were collected and characterized using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, UV-vis and fluorescence spectroscopy, high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS), and size exclusion chromatography (SEC).

Antioxidant capacity (AOC) was assessed using the ABTS assay. Hydrophobic fractions, comprising over 50% of the eluted material, showed markedly enhanced AOC values (0.9–1.4 mmol TE/g), compared to hydrophilic fractions and the parent FA sample (0.65 μ mol ABTS^{•+}/mg). The increase in antioxidant activity correlated strongly with molecular parameters indicative of aromatic and conjugated structures, particularly condensed tannins and lignin-like compounds, as identified by HRMS. A strong correlation ($R^2 = 0.96$) was also observed between AOC values and the fluorescence asymmetry parameter (ASM350), indicating the utility of optical methods for rapid AOC estimation.

To deepen the interpretation of the relationship between chemical structure and antioxidant activity, the same dataset was used to construct a predictive linear regression model based on the contribution of condensed tannins to the FA molecular profile. The resulting equation, $\text{AOC (mmol TE/g)} = 2.6 \times \text{condensed tannins} + 0.29$ ($R^2 = 0.92$), accurately described the AOC response based on the Van Krevelen diagram-derived abundance of condensed tannin-like structures. Model validation using HRMS data for four selected FA fractions demonstrated strong agreement between predicted and experimental AOC values, underscoring the robustness of the approach.

Given the sensitivity of optical properties to conjugated aromatic structures, further correlation analysis was conducted between AOC and fluorescence parameters. A particularly strong inverse relationship was found with ASM350 ($R^2 = 0.96$), reflecting a systematic increase in both red-band fluorescence intensity and antioxidant capacity as the content of conjugated phenolic structures increased. This finding supports the use of one-dimensional fluorescence spectroscopy as a rapid, non-destructive proxy for antioxidant activity in FA-based materials. The consistency of the ASM350–AOC correlation with direct FT-ICR MS data further confirms its applicability for quality control of commercial FA products.

Acknowledgements: This research was financially supported by the Russian Science Foundation grant no. 21-73-20202.

Molecular composition of dissolved organic matter in the Siberian Arctic Shelf: evidence of permafrost influence from FT-ICR MS analysis

Khreptugova A.N.¹, Petrov K.V.¹, Starr S.², Spencer R.³, Semiletov I.P.⁴, Perminova I.V.¹

¹Lomonosov Moscow State University, Department of Chemistry, Moscow, Russia,
khreptugova@mail.ru

²Department of Biological Sciences, The University of Alabama, SEC, 300 Hackberry Lane,
Tuscaloosa, AL 35487, U.S.A.

³NHFML Geochemistry Group and Department of Earth, Ocean, and Atmospheric Science, FSU,
Tallahassee, Florida 32306, U.S.A.

⁴POI, Far Eastern Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 43 Baltic Street, Vladivostok,
Russia

Keywords: dissolved organic matter, Fourier transform ion cyclotron resonance mass spectrometry, Arctic Shelf seas, permafrost thaw, molecular composition
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17322457

The Arctic Shelf seas receive large fluxes of dissolved organic matter (DOM) from major Siberian rivers—Ob, Lena, Yenisei, Kolyma and Indigirka—whose discharge is increasingly influenced by permafrost degradation. This study aimed to assess spatial variability in DOM composition and optical properties across three key river–shelf systems: Ob–Kara Sea, Lena–Laptev Sea, and Indigirka–East Siberian Sea. A total of 109 DOM extracts were obtained aboard the R/V Akademik Mstislav Keldysh during the AMK-82 expedition (October 2020) and analyzed using 21 T Fourier transform ion cyclotron resonance mass spectrometry (FT-ICR MS).

DOM samples from the Kara Sea exhibited the lowest compositional heterogeneity, with $11,327 \pm 2,484$ molecular formulas dominated by CHO compounds ($74.1 \pm 6.2\%$), higher average molecular weights ($M_n = 629 \pm 48$ Da), and elevated double bond equivalents ($DBE_n = 14.6 \pm 1.5$), indicating a prevalence of condensed aromatic structures. In contrast, DOM from the Laptev and East Siberian seas showed increased molecular diversity ($12,486 \pm 1,697$ and $12,400 \pm 2,110$ formulas, respectively), lower CHO contributions ($\sim 65\%$), and greater abundance of nitrogen- and sulfur-containing formulas (CHON: 24–26%; CHONS: 9–10%). Samples from the Lena river discharge zone were particularly enriched in CHON ($32.5 \pm 5.6\%$) and CHONS ($14.8 \pm 5.0\%$) formulas and showed reduced CHO contribution ($54.5 \pm 7.7\%$), lower molecular weights ($M_n = 530 \pm 40$ Da), and DBE_n (11.6 ± 1.0). These patterns suggest inputs of aliphatic, biolabile compounds—such as peptides, amino acids, and heterocycles—likely derived from thawing permafrost deposits mobilized by riverine flow.

Hydrolyzable tannins were the dominant class across all regions (40–60%), followed by lignins (20–45%), terpenoids (2–15%), and carbohydrates (2–10%). Significant differences in chemotype distribution between regions were confirmed by ANOVA and Tukey’s test ($p < 0.05$). DOM near the Lena River outflow showed lower contributions of condensed ($2.6 \pm 1.0\%$) and hydrolyzable tannins ($48.2 \pm 3.7\%$) and elevated proportions of lignins ($30.2 \pm 0.2\%$), terpenoids ($10.2 \pm 1.5\%$), and carbohydrates ($7.3 \pm 1.0\%$) compared to other shelf areas, reflecting a shift toward more aliphatic composition.

Principal component analysis (PCA) of molecular data further distinguished the Lena river influenced DOM samples along PC1 (53.08% of variance), driven by higher H/C ratios and aliphatic components. PC2 (11.49%) reflected variation in aromaticity and oxidation state. These findings suggest that the molecular signature of DOM in the Lena River discharge area may reflect inputs influenced by thawing permafrost, contributing biogeochemically distinct compounds to the shelf waters.

Acknowledgements: The work was carried out within the framework of the State Task 122040600057-3.

Study of the effectiveness of soil purification from petroleum products using humic substances

Kozhamuratova U.M.¹, Kassenova Zh.M.¹, Malgazhdarova A.B.¹, Kazankapova M.K.¹, Bekbosynov A.¹, Yermagambet B.T.¹

¹Institute of Coal Chemistry and Technology" LLP, Astana, Kazakhstan, coaltech@bk.ru

Keywords: Oil-contaminated soil, humic substances, bioremediation, soil purification
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17322638

One of the promising approaches in this context is the use of humic substances — natural macromolecules with high sorption capacity, capable of binding heavy metals and organic pollutants. In addition, humates stimulate the development of soil microflora and contribute to the restoration of the humus layer. Studies have shown that the combination of humates with active microorganisms significantly increases the efficiency of oil-contaminated soil remediation [1].

Table 1. Results of the mass fraction of petroleum products in the soil on days 5, 30, 60, and 90 of the experiment after treatment with potassium humate-based biopreparations

Model name	Mass fraction of petroleum products in soil sample, mg / kg, 5 days	Mass fraction of petroleum products in soil sample, mg / kg, 30 days	Mass fraction of petroleum products in soil sample, mg / kg, 60 days	Mass fraction of petroleum products in soil sample, mg / kg, 90 days	Content of petroleum products, %	Degree of purification, %
Original oil contaminated soil	86.528	86.528	86.528	86.528	100	0
Basic potassium humate 50%	83.600	61.300	17.600	12.300	2.62	85.78
Potassium humate+Si 50%	86.900	64.300	20.300	15.200	3.96	82.43
Potassium humate+NPK 50%	85.200	63.000	19.600	16.400	5.21	81.05

Figure 1. Determination of petroleum products in soil

After 90 days, the content of petroleum products significantly decreased. The highest effect was shown by basic potassium humate (purification — 85.78%). Compositions with Si and NPK provided 82.43% and 81.05%, respectively. This confirms the potential of humic substances for the remediation of contaminated soils.

Acknowledgements. This research has been funded by the Science Committee of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan (Grant No. AR19679324. Research and reclamation of oil-contaminated lands with humic substances).

References

1. Vuković, M., Domanovac, T., Briki, F. Removal of humic substances by biosorption // Journal of Environmental Sciences - 2008 – P. 1423-1428.

Changes in the humus composition of dark chestnut soils in the post-meliorative period

Kushnareva A.V.¹, Bezuglova O.S.²

¹Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment of the Rostov Region, Rostov-on-Don, Russia, avknadzor@list.ru

²Southern Federal University, Rostov-on-Don, Russia

Keywords: Humus, rice crop rotation

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17322796

The fractional composition of soil humus is an important characteristic of changes occurring in the soil due to agrogenic impact. We studied the post-meliorative state of dark chestnut soil in a rice crop rotation. Twenty years of using the soil for field crops after 38 years of growing rice on it had a drastic effect on the humus content and its qualitative composition.

Before irrigation, the humus content in dark chestnut soil according to P.A. Sadimenko (1966) in the topsoil horizon (0–20), on average, was 3.73%, the humus composition was fulvate-humate. As compared to 1952, a significant increase in the humus content in the topsoil horizon was observed in the rice crop rotation soil by 2002, reaching 4.61%. By 2023, in the soil of the area excluded from rice crop rotation, the humus content decreased by 0.59% in the A1 topsoil horizon, which is 20.8% from the starting point in 2002, and remained practically at the same level in the subsoil horizon. This trend is natural, since an increase in temperature and a decrease in soil moisture always contribute to the mineralization of humus and organic residues. Changes in the humus composition of dark chestnut soil also occurred under the influence of irrigation: in 2002 humus had a humate-fulvate composition according to the classification of D.S. Orlov. Down the profile, the FA content decreased, although the opposite picture is usually observed in dark chestnut soils. This tendency of humus shift towards the increased fulvic acids content is confirmed by literature data for irrigated soils, especially under rice (Gutorova, 2020). In 2023, after 20 years of dry land and cultivation of field crops, a sharp decrease in the proportion of fulvic acids in the humus composition is observed compared to 2002. Although from the period when the soil was irrigated, a higher content of fulvic acids in the upper horizon remains, the FC-1 fraction, as well as calcium fulvates (FC-2), decreases in the composition of fulvic acids to the greatest extent. The humic acid content varies across the profile, reaching its maximum in the middle part of the profile: in 2023 at a depth of 18–30 cm (23.12%), in 2002 – at a depth of 35–45 cm (31.9%). The humic acid content increases slightly in the topsoil horizon. At the same time, in deeper horizons it is significantly lower than it was in 2002. Nevertheless, due to a more significant decrease in the proportion of fulvic acids, the $C_{HA}:C_{FA}$ ratio increases and humus type shifts from fulvate and humate-fulvate to a fulvate-humate type throughout the profile. The share of non-hydrolyzable residue (humins) increased in 2023 compared to 2002 by more than 2 times in topsoil horizon, 1.6 times in the midsoil horizon and 1.4 times in the subsoil.

Thus, the change in hydrothermal and oxidation-reduction regimes contributes to the fixation of humic acids and the formation of strong bonds with the mineral part of the soil. Perhaps, this occurs during the transformation of the mineralogical composition of dark chestnut soil.

References

1. Gutorova O.A. Current state of soil fertility in rice agrolandscapes of Kuban and the trend of its change in the process of agricultural use: diss. ... Doctor of Agricultural Sciences, Krasnodar, 2020. 509 p.
2. Sadimenko P.A. Soils of the south-eastern regions of the Rostov region, Rostov University Press, 1966. 128 p.

A new approach to assessing the content of natural hydrocarbons in soils

Lodygin E.¹, Nesterov B.¹, Alekseev I.¹

¹Institute of Biology, FIC Komi Sci. Centre Ur. Br. RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia, lodigin@ib.komisc.ru

Keywords: hydrocarbon background, soil monitoring, GIS technologies, taiga, tundra
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17322905

In the context of the active development of oil and gas resources in Russia's northern territories, it is particularly important to develop scientifically sound approaches to assessing the natural background of hydrocarbons (HCs) in soils. Current standards do not consider natural climatic zoning, which often results in an inaccurate assessment of soil contamination in the Arctic and Subarctic regions. This article therefore proposes a new approach to ecological and hygienic assessment of natural HC content. This approach is based on determining background concentrations and identifying patterns of accumulation in the main soil types in the European north.

The study focused on Cryosols, Histosols, Fluvisols, Podzols, Retisols, Spodosols, Stagnosols and Umbrisols in the arctic and subarctic regions of the Komi Republic. Samples were collected using a route method that took landscape gradients from automorphic to hydromorphic conditions into account. HC concentrations were determined by measuring the fluorescence intensity of the hexane extract using a Fluorat-02-03M analyser. To systematise the results, a database and a map of the spatial distribution of natural HCs were created using GIS technologies (ArcView GIS 3.2a).

The results showed that organic soil horizons serve as a geochemical barrier and an integral indicator of aerotechnogenic loading, accumulating the highest concentrations of HCs. The content of HC depends on the granulometric composition of the parent rocks, the landscape's relief, and the type of pedogenesis. Maximum values are characteristic of accumulative and eluvial-accumulative landscapes (Retisols), while minimum values are characteristic of eluvial soils (Cryosols and Podzols). Profile differentiation is more pronounced in loamy soils (Retisols) and weaker in sandy soils (Podzols), where HCs are more uniformly distributed and leach more easily from podzolic horizons. Background HC concentration ranges vary widely, from 3.4 mg/kg in Haplic Cryosols to 40 mg/kg in Gleyic Stagnic Retisols.

As a key element of the new approach, threshold values are proposed for ecological and hygienic purposes, rather than average concentrations of HCs. These threshold values are defined as the upper 95th percentile for each soil type. This criterion takes natural fluctuations into account and excludes extreme values, ensuring a more accurate assessment of background HC content.

The resulting data and methodology can be used in engineering and environmental surveys and environmental impact assessments of the drilling, construction and operation of oil and gas facilities in high latitudes. They can also be used to improve standards for petroleum HC content, taking regional characteristics into account. The created database and map of natural HC distribution will form the basis for expanding the soil monitoring system and predicting pollution risks. In future, the methodology could be adapted for use with soils in other regions and supplemented with information on other classes of pollutants. This would enable a more comprehensive assessment of the resilience of soil ecosystems to human impact.

Acknowledgements. This work was supported by the RSF (no. 24-24-00144).

Extraction and fractionation of lipid components of soil by chromatographic methods

Lyu-Lyan-Min E.I., Shamrikova E.V., Gruzdev I.V., Zhangurov E.V.

Institute of Biology Komi SC UrD RAS, Syktyvkar, Russian Federation, gruzdeva.e@ib.komisc.ru

Keywords: aliphatic acids, aliphatic alcohols, alkanes, gas chromatography/mass spectrometry
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17323311

The maintenance of soil structure, as well as the preservation of its biodiversity, depends on the contribution of various fractions of soil organic matter, where the most important is the lipid fraction, which is directly related to the soil microbiome [1]. The lipid components (LC) of the soil include numerous organic compounds, ranging from complex molecules (phospholipids, peptidolipids, glycolipids, etc.) to simpler ones such as alkanes, ketones, alcohols, and carboxylic acids, which often act as indicators of chemical and biochemical processes occurring in the soil [2].

The accelerated solvent extraction (ASE) method was used to extract LC of the soil, allowing the use of organic extractants at elevated temperature and pressure. Heating (up to 150 °C) accelerates the extraction process, while high pressure (up to 12 MPa) allows the extractant to be kept in a liquid state over a wide temperature range. We have shown that only the extractant temperature has a significant effect on the extraction of organic compounds of different classes from the soil using the ASE method. Chromatographic methods are traditionally used to analyze soil extracts for the content of LC. However, the use of even highly efficient capillary columns is often accompanied by the imposition of chromatographic peaks of the components, which leads to unreliable information about the qualitative and quantitative composition. An increase in the selectivity of the determination of LC of the soil can be achieved by their preliminary fractionation. The method of column adsorption chromatography was used to fractionate the isolated LC. The two most common sorbents were considered: silica gel and aluminum oxide.

Unlike the known approaches, the extract was mixed with a sorbent and evaporated directly on the sorbent, which avoids over-dissolution of the residue and preserves the volatile components of the extract. After the transfer of the sorbent (Al_2O_3) to the column, the alkane hydrocarbon fraction was isolated with hexane.

Repeated elution of the sorbed components with diethyl ether allows us to isolate the fraction of higher aliphatic alcohols.

The fraction of fatty acids was isolated directly from the sorbent by direct methanolysis, which eliminates the stage of elution of acids and ensures their quantitative determination.

The developed approach was applied to the analysis of LC of soils of the Polar Urals on carbonate rocks (Bolshoy Paipudynsky Ridge).

The research was carried out within the framework of the RNF grant № 24-27-00231 «Carbonate soil-permafrost geosystems of the Polar Urals: polygenesis, evolution, classification»

References

1. Willers C., Jansen van Rensburg P.J., Claassens S. Phospholipid fatty acid profiling of microbial communities—a review of interpretations and recent applications // *J. Appl. Microbiol.* 2015. V. 119. № 5. P. 1207–1218. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jam.12902>
2. Otto A., Shunthirasingham C., Simpson M. J.A comparison of plant and microbial biomarkers in grassland soils from the Prairie Ecozone of Canada // *Org. Geochem.* 2005. V. 36. № 13. P. 425–448. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.orggeochem.2004.09.008>.

Is it possible to harmonize the SOC measurement? Results of the 1st Eurasian GLOSOLAN PT (2023/2024)

Shamrikova E., Vanchikova E., Kondratenok B., Lapteva E., Kostrova S., Tumanova E., Zonova T., Lyu-Lyan-Min E., Kyzyurova E., Bondarenko N.
Institute of Biology Komi SC UrD RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia, shamrikovaelena@yandex.ru

Keywords: soil organic carbon, measurement methods, harmonization of methods
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17332021

Soil organic carbon (SOC) is a system of specific and non-specific organic compounds. There is no consensus on the nature and origin of humic substances (HS) in soils [1]. The development of modern methods expands the understanding of the structure of humic substances, but the initial stage of their characterization is the measurement of SOC. The problem of comparability of SOC values obtained by different methods remains and can be solved by harmonizing them. The National Reference Laboratory of the Russian Federation in the GLOSOLAN system (FAO) (<https://ib.komisc.ru/rusolan/>) for 25 laboratories from six countries conducted the 1st Eurasian professional tests (PT) for measuring SOC using various methods: reference – Dry combustion on an elemental C, N-analyzer (DC) [3]; Tyurin (T) and Walkley-Black (W-B) methods with photometric termination [2] and the method for measuring the loss of mass on ignition of soil (LOI). The analysis of the results of PT allowed us to draw the following conclusions.

1. The established permissible relative error of SOC measurements by the dichromatometric method equal to 20%, as well as the introduction of correction factors in the T and W-B methods equal to 1.15 and 1.3, respectively, allow obtaining harmonized measurement results by any of the three methods: DC, T and W-B. It is necessary to develop a reliable method for converting SOC obtained by the LOI method taking into account the factor 0.58 with other analytical techniques. Otherwise, comparison of SOC measured by this method with the results of other methods should be carried out with great caution.

2. The factors reducing the accuracy of SOC measurements by the T and W-B methods were identified:

- correctness of the assessment of the characteristics of the calibration function;
- selection of the sample of the analyzed soil. The criterion for selecting the soil mass is the compliance of the optical density of the solution obtained after SOC oxidation with the optimal value from 0.05 to 0.5;
- a method for separating the solid and liquid phases after oxidation of the carbon of organic compounds with potassium dichromate. Centrifugation is a priority for separating the phases of the mixture;
- it is recommended to recalculate SOC for an absolutely dry sample of soil. Fluctuations in room humidity cause a relative shift in SOC of an air-dry sample from an absolutely dry one of the same sample by up to 6%.

The work was carried out within the framework of the state budget theme of the Soil Science Department of the Institute of Biology Komi SC UrD RAS No. 125021902454-1.

References

1. Zavarzina A. G., Danchenko N. N., Demin V. V., Artemyeva Z. S., Kogut B. M. Humic substances: hypotheses and reality (a review) // Eurasian Soil Sci. 2021, 54, 1826-185.
2. Metodika izmereniy massovoy doli ugleroda organicheskikh soyedineniy i organicheskogo veshchestva fotometricheskimi metodami (metody Tyurin i Walkley-Black) / № 88-17641-001-2020 / Ye. Vanchikova et al. Syktyvkar, IB Komi NTS UrO RAN. 2020. 51 s.
3. Metodika izmereniy massovoy doli azota, ugleroda, organicheskogo veshchestva na elementnom analizatore YEA 1110 (CHNS-O) / № 88-17641-004-2016 / Vanchikova Ye. et al. Syktyvkar, IB Komi NTS UrO RAN. 29 s.

Stabilization of soil organic matter of palsa bogs as a response to climate change in Holocene

Vasilevich R.S.¹, Zhrebker A.Y.², Kuznetsov O.L.³

¹Institute of Biology Komi SC UrD RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia, vasilevich.r.s@ib.komisc.ru

²Project Center of Omics Technologies and Advanced Mass Spectrometry, Moscow, Russia

³Institute of Biology, Karelian Research Centre, RAS, Petrozavodsk, Russia

Keywords: European Arctic, relict permafrost peatlands, climatic conditions, humic acids, molecular composition

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17332130

Permafrost degradation in palsa bog ecosystems has a significant impact on global and regional carbon balances. The stability and biodegradability of soil organic matter (SOM) are crucial parameters for accurately assessing current and future carbon stocks. It is postulated that the extent of SOM stabilization in perennially frozen peatlands is currently underestimated. The mechanisms by which lignin biodegradation, subsequent demethylation, carboxylation and formation of condensed transformation products in the molecular composition of humic acids (HAs) occur under anaerobic conditions in peatland ecosystems remain essential and poorly understood in modern scientific research. It is also imperative to consider the vectors of stabilization of HAs beyond the mineral matrix (humus formation in oligotrophic conditions) and their resistance to fungal decomposition as key factors.

The ¹³C NMR and high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) methods have been employed to elucidate the principal pathways of SOM stabilization in the peat deposit of palsa bogs in the European Arctic. Extremes of labile/condensed constituents and structural moieties have been found to be related to climatic and hydrological conditions during different periods of the Holocene. The highest content of condensed structures is observed in the peat layers formed during the Atlantic and Early Subboreal periods. The initial stage of SOM stabilization includes decomposition of plant residues, formation of (pro)humic substances (HSs) molecules from high-molecular-weight precursors, and primary transformation of HS molecules with degradation of the most labile fragments. Older HAs, which underwent intense degradation were enriched in the N,S-containing components as compared to surface layers. This is in turn accompanied by an overall decrease in the proportion of unoxidized aliphatic and carbohydrate fragments. A substantial proportion of highly condensed compounds were identified in HAs by HRMS. It was suggested that aromatic and condensed molecules contain long-chain substituents that contribute to the content of aliphatic carbon. The ratio of pentosans to hexosans in HAs is demonstrated to increase down the peat profile as a consequence of the redistribution of the dominant peat formers. The HA branching indices demonstrate a significant transformation of long-chain structures and an increase in the contribution of substituted aliphatic fragments in the HA structure. This allows for the reconstruction of past climates and prediction of the mechanisms of SOM stabilization under modern climatic changes.

Acknowledgements. The reported study was funded by the Federal budget of Russia, within the framework of the research topic of the Institute of Biology (No. 125021902454-1).

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and phenanthrene derivatives in long-term stored bark and wood waste

Yakovleva E.V., Gabov D.N., Vasilevich R.S., Gruzdev I.V., Shchemelinina T.N., Anchugova E.M., Gunderina E.D.
Institute of Biology Komi SC UrD RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia

Keywords: polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, derivatives, bark and wood waste
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17332192

This study examined the levels of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and phenanthrene derivatives in bark and wood waste (BWW) from the Syktyvkar LDK landfill using HPLC-FLD/DAD and GC/MS methods. The waste over a period of approximately 1950 to 2010. BWW samples were taken from two cores at depth of up to 27 meters.

Significant levels of PAHs and phenanthrene derivatives were detected in the BWW (figure). Naphthalene and acenaphthene were evenly distributed throughout the profile of both cores. The content of heavy PAHs and derivatives increased sharply in the lower part of the profiles, probably due to their pedogenic formation during the waste decomposition under conditions of high temperature and high substrate moisture. These conditions promote the reductive condensation processes involving lignin, humic acids, and resin acids. An inverse relationship was observed in the accumulation of PAHs and phenanthrene derivatives in the lower layers of the BWW landfill. The elevated concentrations of heavy PAH structures and derivatives in the upper part of the profile of core 1 may be associated with combustion processes. Principle Component Analysis revealed that the accumulation of PAHs and phenanthrene derivatives depended primarily on the pH and moisture content of the waste, primarily in well 2. A greater number of the compounds studied were detected under conditions of high moisture content and neutral pH. In the lower layers of the BWW, the total toxicity equivalency concentration exceeded the maximum permissible concentrations for benz[a]pyrene in soils by up to ninefold. The upper layers exhibited a low degree of environmental risk to living organisms and natural ecosystems, whereas the lower layers presented a moderate degree of risk.

Figure. Distribution of PAHs and phenanthrene derivatives in cores 1 and 2 of bark and wood waste

This work was supported by the State Assignment of the IB FRC Komi SC UB RAS, (No. 125021902454-1 and No.125021201993-3).

2. The role of humic substances and components of soil organic matter in the carbon cycle of terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems

Organic matter of clear-cut soils

Bondarenko N.N., Kyzyurova E.V., Lapteva E.M.

Institute of Biology of Komi Science Centre of the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, BondNikropoINik@mail.ru

Keywords: podzolic soils, humic and fulvic acids, low-molecular water-soluble organic compounds
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17333247

Final felling is one of the significant factors influencing changes in the structure and component composition of natural ecosystems. Soil resistance to anthropogenic impact is closely related to the qualitative and quantitative characteristics of soil organic matter (SOM). SOM is a set of organic compounds of different nature and molecular composition. A comprehensive assessment of SOM is one of the leading tasks of soil science [1]. However, the features of changes in the component composition of SOM in the process of natural restoration of woody vegetation remain poorly studied, which predetermined the purpose of this work.

The direct objects of the study were forest litters of the bilberry-green moss spruce forest (PP-1) and random uneven-aged deciduous-coniferous biocenoses formed after final felling in 2001-2002 (PP-2) and 1969-1970 (PP-3). Analytical studies were carried out according to generally accepted methods in soil science. The total content of carbon (C_{total}) and nitrogen (N_{total}) was determined by gas chromatography on a CNHS-O analyzer, the content of carbon of water-soluble organic compounds (C_{os}) was determined by high-temperature catalytic oxidation on a TOC VCPH total carbon analyzer. The mass concentration of low-molecular POC was estimated by gas chromatography and chromatograph mass spectrometry (GC/MS) [2].

In the PP-1 and PP-2 plots, the forest litters belong to the category of strongly and very strongly acidic soils, the upper horizons of the forest litter of PP-3 are characterized as slightly acidic, the lower part retains a strongly acidic reaction of the environment. The proportion of carbon C_{boc} from C_{ob} is 11-30%, the forest litters of the studied plots belong to the category of soils with an ultra-high content of WOC. In the PP-1 and PP-2 plots, the content of C_{boc} decreases with depth, in the PP-3 plot, the subhorizons of the forest litter are characterized by close values. More significant differences between the plots are observed when comparing the carbon share of the identified WOC. A similar pattern of distribution of the carbon share of the identified WOC has forest litters of the PP-1 and PP-2 plots, however, the quantitative content in the PP-2 plot is twice as small. The PP-3 plot is characterized by the maximum values, while no clear differentiation by the subhorizons of the forest litter is observed. The identified components of the WOC are dominated by carbohydrates, in particular hexoses. The process of restoration of woody vegetation is accompanied by an increase in their content. For the initial stages of restoration of woody vegetation, an increase in the proportion of alcohols in the composition of the identified WOC is noted. The content of the identified acids varies greatly depending on both the time of logging and the subhorizon of the forest litter. The mass fraction of C_{total} is within 30-48%, N_{total} - 1.4-2.1%. Despite the increase in the proportion of nitrogen in the forest litter of the soils of the clear-cut areas, the value of the C/N ratio (20 - 32) indicates their very low enrichment.

References

1. Zsolnay A. Dissolved organic matter: artefacts, definitions and functions // *Geoderma*. 2003. V. 113. P. 187–209. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061\(02\)00361-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061(02)00361-0)
2. Gmach M.R., Cherubin M.R., Kaiser K., Cerri C.E.P. Processes that influence dissolved organic matter in the soil: a review // *Scientia Agricola*. 2020. V. 77.

Current issues of Humus science

Dergacheva M.

Institute of Soil Science and Agrochemistry SB RAS, Novosibirsk, Russia, mid555@yandex.ru

Keywords: system of humus substances, humic acids, specificity of molecular properties, role of matrix, self-regulation, reasons of stability

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17333300

An analysis of the nearly 250-year history of the formation and development of the theory of soil humus shows that the most controversial (and therefore relevant at all times) problems in this area of knowledge are the reality of the existence of humic substances as special natural formations, evidence of the specificity of their structure and properties, the reasons for their stability over time, as well as their participation in the implementation of the most important ecosystem functions. The study of soil humus at different levels of its organization for more than 50 years allowed me to develop and substantiate the concept of humus as a natural open system of interconnected humic substances, possessing the properties of self-organization, self-regulation and performing in its entirety a number of integral systemic functions, such as participation in ensuring fertility, forming a soil profile, stability over time, preserving information and others. The main provisions of this concept, considered mainly at the level of humus composition, were first presented in a holistic form in the eighties of the last century (Dergacheva, 1984, 1989). Further study of soil humus as a natural open (dissipative) self-organizing and self-regulating system revealed (Dergacheva, 2018) that humic acids (HA) have the most specific parameters and relatively narrow ranges of variation of quantitative characteristics within different formation conditions. They have a single structural principle, regardless of the source of humification, but differ significantly from each other at the level of quantitative indicators. The close relationships between different quantitative parameters of HA and the climate indicators of local areas of their location, revealed using monofactorial series, made it possible to determine the indicator significance of their main molecular characteristics when assessing the conditions of the natural environment that forms them, the direction and degree of transformation, as well as stability-variability due to a changing natural environment. Thus, H:C in HA reflects the climatic environment of soil formation, changes in functioning conditions; Its value is well preserved over time and can serve as a reliable indicator in **determining** the bioclimatic conditions of the formation of soils of different ages and paleosols. The O:C ratio reflects the textural state of soils and is closely related to their granulometric composition. The H:C–O:C ratio can serve as a reliable indicator of the classification of soils, differences in horizons with different oxidative-reductive conditions of formation and/or the direction of changes under different impacts on soils. Other HA parameters obtained by different independent spectral methods are closely related to the H:C value, as well as to the climatic indicators of their formation (all correlation coefficients are in the range of 0.75–0.95).

The existing working database, which was used in interpreting the HA study materials, currently contains information on the composition and properties of more than ten thousand HA soils of different ages and formation conditions, as well as climatic parameters for almost every local area of their location. The overall assessment of the specificity of the composition, properties and behavior of humic acids in a changing natural and anthropogenic environment makes it possible to consider HA as a matrix that ensures the preservation of the humic substance system, which performs the main important functions in ecosystems and the biosphere as a whole.

The work was carried out under the state assignment of the IPA SB RAS with the financial support of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Russian Federation (project No. 121031700309 1).

The impact of harvesting operation on Albic Retisols in the middle taiga of the Komi Republic

Dymov A.A.¹, Kutuyavin I.N.¹, Startsev V.V.¹, Gorbach N.M.¹, Severgina D.A.¹, Pausova I.V.¹, Vachruchev L.A.¹, Dubrovskiy Yu.A.¹, Nechaev R.A.¹, Arzubov P.A.¹, Ogorodnia S.A.¹, Osipov A.F.¹

¹Institute of Biology Komi SC UrB RAS, Syktyvkar, Russian Federation

Keywords: boreal forest, soil organic matter, carbon pools

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17333330

Forest soils perform important biospheric functions related to the atmosphere, hydrosphere, lithosphere, and the biosphere as a whole. Forest ecosystems are involved in the regulation of carbon and nitrogen cycles in the biosphere, influence the water and temperature regimes of soils, contribute to the formation of river flows and water balance, and control the intensity of pedogenesis and formation of the soil profiles. Soils of forest ecosystems are the major player in the energy processes in the biosphere and sensitively respond to the occurring changes. Cuttings are the most important factor that influences the forest-forming process. The replacement of conifers by leaved tree species has taken place within considerable areas in the northeast of the European part of Russia. A specific feature of the Komi Republic is natural restoration of tree species takes place in cutting areas. The aim of this work is to assess changes in Retisols in the first decades after clear-cutting carried out using modern logging equipment.

The objects of the study were located in the middle taiga of the European part of Russian Federation. To assess the consequences, blueberry spruce and birch forests formed on Retisols in the clear cutting area of eight and eighteen years were selected. It has been found that heavy logging equipment significantly changes forest soils. About 20 percent of the logging areas are represented by skidding trails with mechanically changed soils. Depending on the location in the landscape, in the first decades the soils may be over-watered or, on the contrary, drier compared to the background objects. Logging activities significantly affect the carbon pool in woody vegetation. It was found that coarse woody debris formed during logging decomposes to a significant extent in the first decades after logging. An increase in soil respiration on skidding trails by 1.7–2.5 times was revealed compared to undisturbed areas. Carbon stocks in soils remain fairly stable and are less susceptible to change.

Acknowledgements. The research was carried out as part of the most important innovative project of national importance “Development of a system for ground-based and remote monitoring of carbon pools and greenhouse gas fluxes in the territory of the Russian Federation, ensuring the creation of recording data systems on the fluxes of climate-active substances and the carbon budget in forests and other terrestrial ecological systems” (Registration number: 123030300031-6).

The role of fires in the transformation of soil organic matter

Dymov A.A.¹, Pausova I.V.¹, Gorbach N.M.¹

¹Institute of Biology Komi SC UrB RAS, Syktyvkar, Russian Federation

Keywords: soil organic matter, fire, boreal forest, PyrC, BPCAs

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17333368

A significant part of the carbon in Northern ecosystems is concentrated in soils. Fires are one of the permanent and significant factors affecting ecosystems. The impact of fires on ecosystems is complex and can have both a positive effect on individual tree species and contribute to significant degradation of ecosystems. Together with climate, the pyrogenic factor controls the age structure and mosaic nature of the vegetation cover, its further evolution and the flows of matter and energy and soil and ecosystem carbon pools. The frequency of fires in the boreal forests of the European North of Russia varies from one or two per century to one or two per millennium. In addition, current climate changes lead to active burning of ecosystems that are weakly susceptible to fires in normal years. However, the role of fires in the formation and transformation of soil organic matter is rarely taken into account when assessing soil organic matter. The purpose of this work is to reveal the possibilities of various methods for assessing the properties of soil organic matter due to the influence of fires and to reveal the possible consequences of fire impact on the properties of SOM.

The biomass of woody vegetation and ground cover plants, litter are most exposed to pyrogenic effects. The determining factors for the compounds formed during a fire are the initial biochemical composition, temperature, and oxygen availability during the combustion process. The bioclimatic conditions of the Northern landscapes of Eurasia contribute to the prevalence of low-intensity fires in which partial combustion of biomass occur. To assess the pyrogenic impact on soil organic matter, methods are often used that allow identifying compounds and structures with an aromatic nature. Chromatographic approaches are most widely used, allowing for the isolation of polycyclic aromatic compounds (PAHs), benzene polycarboxylic acids (BPCAs) and the capabilities of nuclear magnetic resonance are widely used. It is shown that the methods used have a number of limitations and advantages. The most correct way to judge the composition of pyrogenic organic matter is to judge by the total concentration of BPCAs. The content of PAHs can mark the pyrogenic impact, the greatest indicative value is played by the concentrations of two and three-cyclic PAHs. For a number of soils, pyrogenesis is an important factor determining the aromaticity of soil organic matter, the content of PAHs and, in general, determines the pyrogenic path of transformation of organic compounds.

Acknowledgements. This work was supported by Russian Science Foundation, project no.25-17-00054 “Nature-like and Anthropogenic Technologies for Accumulation of Stable Carbon Forms in Forest Soils” <https://rscf.ru/project/25-17-00054/>.

References

1. Dymov A.A., Startsev V.V., Gorbach N.M., Pausova I.N., Gabov D.N., Donnerhack O. Comparison of the methods for determining pyrogenically modified carbon compounds // *Eurasian Soil Science*. 2021. 54(11). 1668–1680. DOI: 10.1134/S1064229321110065.
2. Dymov A.A., Startsev V.V., Milanovsky E.Yu., Valdes-Korovkin I.A., Farkhodov Yu.R., Yudina A.V., Donnerhack O., Guggenberger G. Soils and soil organic matter transformations during the two years after a low-intensity surface fire (Subpolar Ural, Russia) // *Geoderma*. 2021. 404. 115278. DOI: 10.1016/j.geoderma.2021.115278.

The dynamics of water-soluble organic matter in constructed soils of different composition

Gorbov S.N.^{1,2}, Skripnikov P.N.^{1,2}, Tishchenko S.A.²

¹Sirius University of Science and Technology, Sirius Federal Territory, Russia,
gorbov.sn@talantiuspeh.ru

²Southern Federal University, Rostov-on-Don, Russia

Keywords: water-soluble organic matter, humic substances, constructed soil, Urbic Technosols, organic carbon

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17333541

Due to the increasing human impact on the environment, the study of urban soils, especially constructed soils, has become more important. One significant aspect of this research is the investigation of organic matter dynamics and composition including the water-soluble organic matter (WSOM), the most labile and biochemically active humic substances in soil.

Various transformation degrees of constructed soil profiles, with the obligatory presence of a surface recultivation-humus horizon named RAT are studied. The RAT horizon is usually formed by humus-accumulative masses (AU) of Haplic Chernozem (calcic). The content of total organic carbon (TOC) and the content of WSOM were determined by high-temperature catalytic combustion using a TOC-L CPN Shimadzu carbon analyzer. WSOM was eluted by cold and hot extraction. Statistical processing includes data descriptive statistics, as well as the calculation of the Spearman's correlation coefficient (r).

The TOC distribution in the constructed soil profile clearly has reflects the morphological bimodality of the soil profile. The highest TOC content occurs in surface horizons and buried humus layers of native soil. Anthropogenic surface horizons are characterized by a chaotic distribution of organic carbon, due to their genesis and the properties of filling materials, while the buried natural layers have shown a gradual decrease in organic carbon content. A strong negative correlation was found between TOC content and depth in Haplic Chernozems (Transportic, Technic) ($r=-0.75$) and moderate correlation in Urbic Technosols (Terric, Transportic) ($r=-0.64$), compared to a strong correlation inherent for Haplic Chernozem (calcic) ($r=-0.90$). WSOM content has shown a strong direct correlation with TOC content ($r = 0.85$). The profile WSOM distribution was similar to the TOC distribution and had inversions in the profile in case of buried natural profiles. The proportion of WSOM carbon in the TOC pool in all investigated soil was 2.5-5% and it was classified as "very high". In RAT horizon the WSOM carbon proportion was slightly lower ($2.59 \pm 0.67\%$), in the buried natural AU horizon was slightly higher ($3.44 \pm 1.52\%$), but this difference is absence statistically significant.

The composition and genesis of recultivation-humus RAT horizons were determining the specifics of the organic matter distribution in the profile. Despite the significant transformation, there is a significant pool of labile organic matter in constructed soil, including WSOM. This fact indicates the importance of WSOM in the soil formation processes and carbon cycling in urban ecosystems.

Acknowledgements. This work was supported by the grant of the state program of the «Sirius» Federal Territory «Scientific and technological development of the «Sirius» Federal Territory» (Agreement №3-03 date 18.02.2025).

Organic matter of buried soils as a carbon depot

Kovaleva N., Sidorova I., Kovalev I.

Moscow State University, Moscow, Russia, natalia_kovaleva@mail.ru

Keywords: carbon cycle, soil age

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17333589

Buried soils are an undervalued repository of carbon, a witness to the composition of the atmosphere at different time points in the evolution of the biosphere. The aim of the study was to assess the deposit potential of soils buried under archaeological monuments of historical time in the forest-steppe zone. The most humus soils - chernozems - are widespread in this zone.

The objects of the study are located in the central part of Hussian Plain - in the Tambov and Voronezh regions. The buried soils are confined to the Kozlovsky, Urlyapov and Ostrogozhsky ramparts of the Belgorod defensive line. On the mentioned ramparts there are chronocatenas of soils consisting of daytime chernozems on the top of the rampart and in the surrounding landscape, buried chernozems - under the ramparts and meadow-chernozem soils - in the bottom of the defensive ditches.

The research methods included determination of carbon on a CNS analyzer, determination of the isotopic composition of organic carbon on an isotope analyzer, radiocarbon dating of buried soil horizons, and determination of the rate of mineralization of organic matter using the substrate-induced respiration method.

The highest content of organic carbon in the soils of the ramparts is observed in the upper horizon on the rampart itself (about 4 %), approximately the same amount of carbon is in the buried chernozem. Increased carbon content is also characteristic of the cultural layers (2 %). In the background section, this indicator is 2 times less (1.82 %) than on the rampart, as a result of dehumification due to plowing. The enrichment of humus with nitrogen is low and very low (C / N - 12-15). The humus reserves in the surface horizons (100-200 t/ha) are less than those in the buried humus horizons in the body of the ramparts (200-300 t/ha) and are comparable to those in the chernozems buried under the ramparts (140 t/ha).

The dynamics of C-CO₂ formation with a maximum at the beginning of incubation and a gradual slowdown over time indicates a heterogeneous composition of the soil organic matter of buried soils, in which components protected from decomposition predominate. The content of active (potentially mineralizable) organic matter decreases exponentially down the profile, coinciding with the distribution of organic carbon. The organic matter of different soil horizons differs in mineralization rate constants. Most of the parameters characterizing the mineralization potential of soil organic matter (daily and cumulative production of C-CO₂, mineralization intensity, content of potentially mineralizable carbon) decreased in soils from the upper to the lower horizons, and their maximum values were observed in the chernozem-meadow soil.

The results of the carbon isotope analysis show that both the surface and buried soils were formed under the canopy of C-3 vegetation, since the range of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values is within -25.74 to -23.97 ‰ and corresponds to the woody vegetation of the temperate zone. At the same time, the surface horizons demonstrate the lightest values of isotope ratios: from -26.13 to -25.32 ‰. In the chernozems buried under ramparts, the values of isotope ratios are heavier to -23.97 ‰, which indicates episodes of a warm dry climate, apparently accompanied by a decrease in the groundwater level. The radiocarbon age of the chernozem buried under the ramparts is 2510±50 years, and the lower part of the AB horizon on the Tambov Plain was formed in the middle Holocene 6760±90 years ago.

Acknowledgements. The study was supported by grant No. 24-68-00011 from the Russian Science Foundation, <https://rscf.ru/project/24-68-00011/>.

Features of the organization of amino acids in the plant-soil system of marsh ecosystems

Kubik O., Shamrikova E., Deneva S., Panyukov A.

Institute of Biology, FIC Komi Sci. Centre Ur. Br. RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia, kubik-olesia@yandex.ru

Keywords: marsh soils, halophytes, cereals, sedge, amino acids, carbon, nitrogen

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17333618

Amino acids (AAs) play an important role in the nitrogen cycle in the soil: they are part of humus and play a significant role in the process of soil formation. Soil enrichment with amino acids occurs as a result of the decomposition of plant and animal remains.

Using liquid chromatography, quantitative patterns of formation of bound amino acids in marsh soils of the northern seas of the European north-east of Russia have been established Tidalic Fluvisol (Clayic, Ochric) – White Sea coast; Tidalic Fluvisol (Arenic, Ochric, Epiprotosalic), Tidalic Fluvisol (Loamic, Ochric, Epiprotosalic), Tidalic Fluvisol (Arenic, Ochric) – Barents Sea coast [1]. Additionally, the above-ground part of the biomass of species dominant in the ground cover of coastal tundra ecosystems (cereals, sedges, halophytes) was studied.

Neutral amino acids – glycine, alanine, valine, isoleucine, leucine, proline, serine and threonine, tyrosine and phenylalanine, cysteine and methionine, basic amino acids – aspartic and glutamic acids, and acidic amino acids – lysine, histidine, and arginine – were found in all the studied objects. The fairly uniform qualitative composition of AAs hydrolysates of soils of different origins, humic acids of tundra soils, as well as plants and soil microorganisms, is consistent with literature data [2, 3]. Representatives of the above-ground part of the marsh vegetation contain 90-130 g/kg of hydrolysable amino acids, which make a significant contribution to the total content of carbon (C_{org}) and nitrogen (N_{org}) of the biomass - 10-16 and 50-70%, respectively. The biomaterial of plants in saline habitats is more enriched with protein AAs than in marsh soils. The maximum content of amino compounds is characteristic of the surface horizons of soils, decreasing with depth within the range from 60 to 4.5 mg/kg, which is 8-12 and 30-50% of C_{org} and N_{org} of soils, respectively. The total content of all identified amino acids in the objects of study closely correlates with the content of C_{org} and N_{org} in them ($R^2 = 0.94-0.99$). The results indicate a significant contribution of amino acids to the elemental fund of carbon and, especially, nitrogen in soils and phytomass of coastal Arctic territories.

Acknowledgements. The work was carried out within the framework of the state budget theme of the Soil Science Department of the Institute of Biology Komi SC UrD RAS No. 125021902454-1.

References

1. IUSS Working Group WRB. 2022. World Reference Base for Soil Resources. International soil 914 classification system for naming soils and creating legends for soil maps. 4th edition. 915 International Union of Soil Sciences (IUSS), Vienna, Austria.
2. Vasilevich R.S., Beznosikov V.A. Amino acid composition of humic substances in tundra soils // Eurasian Soil Science. 2015. V. 48. P. 593–599. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1064229315060125>
3. Shamrikova E.V., Deneva S.V., Kubik O.S., Panjukov A.N. Nitrogen compounds in the soil of the continental margins of the European Russian Arctic // Eurasian Soil Science. 2020. V. 53. P. 870-881. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1064229320070133>

Qualitative and quantitative characteristics of organic extract from plant materials used in lentil cultivation

Kudryavtsev A.E.¹, Vaganov E.S.², Sorokin A.S.³

¹Altai State Agricultural University, Barnaul, Russian Federation, kae5959@mail.ru

²Aleysky branch of the Federal State Budgetary Institution "RosAgrokhimsluzhba", Aleysk, Russian Federation

³IP Sorokin A.S., Barnaul, Russian Federation

Keywords: agrophytocenosis, extract from plant materials, nutrients

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17333659

Phytocenoses create significantly more primary organic matter, which determines the genesis and, as a consequence, soil fertility, than agrocenoses. Since they form a phytomass with a closed cycle of substances, including a variety of plant material, while in an agrophytocenosis a person takes the bulk of the plant matter with the harvest, and the remaining part is insignificant, and the production process itself depends on the genetic nature of the crop, technological processes, weather conditions, provision of the soil with moisture reserves, nutrients [1]. Organic preparations used in agriculture are promising and in demand. The purpose of the research is a quantitative and qualitative assessment of the extract from plant raw materials that allows compensating for the organic matter necessary in the agrophytocenosis, due to the plant extract of the phytocenosis. The studies were conducted in the chernozem zone of the arid and moderately arid steppe of Altai. The object of the research was green plant extracts of phytocenoses, which were used in the cultivation of lentils and other crops as stimulants and growth regulators. Previously, laboratory studies were conducted in lysimeters using a hardware and software complex that allows online monitoring of such parameters in the soil as temperature, humidity, environmental reaction, mobile nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium [2]. In the production experiment, to regulate growth processes, the plant extract was added during sowing and according to the developed foliar feeding scheme. The quality of the plant extract and its effectiveness for the agrocenosis is determined by a set of factors that affect the completeness and speed of extraction of active substances. The fundamental factor should be considered the component composition, which in the study area in the spring consisted of 80-90% cereals, 10-20% legumes and cruciferous plants, over time, the qualitative composition of the phytocenosis changed, but insignificantly. An important tool in the preparation of the plant extract is grinding green plants, in laboratory conditions, the plant material was chopped to 5-10 cm, and in the production experiment, the plant mass was mown with a combine. A qualitative assessment was carried out in an accredited laboratory using methods for determining organic compounds in plant extracts. It was found that the reaction of the medium is mainly acidic, slightly acidic, sometimes neutral, the carbon content is in the range from 300 g / l to 450 g / l, sugar - 0.1-9.0 g / l, dry residue 1.2-6.2 g / l. The content of macroelements is: total nitrogen - 0.1-1.5 g / l; phosphorus - 0.1-1.0 g / l; potassium - 0.9-5.8 g / l, mesoelements and microelements are present in slightly larger quantities. The content of plant extract depends not only on the component composition of plant mass, but also the extraction mode, the ratio of raw materials and extractant. This approach allows for the saturation of agrocenoses with the necessary nutrients, using extracts of the neighboring phytocenosis.

References

1. Vlasenko O.A. et al. Structure and dynamics of plant matter reserves in the agrocenosis of camelina sativa // Bulletin of KrasSAU. 2019. No. 11 (152). P. 24-29.
2. Kudryavtsev A.E., Sorokin A.S. Modern digital technologies for solving environmental problems and preserving the fertility of soil resources // Agriculture. 2024. No. 8. P. 8-13. DOI 10.24412/0044-3913-2024-8-8-13.

Emission of CO₂ from spruce soils at the Lyalsky test site (Komi Republic)

Kuznetsov M.A., Osipov A.F.

Institute of Biology of Komi Science Centre of the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Syktyvkar, Russia, e-mail: kuznetsov_ma@ib.komisc.ru

Keywords: soil respiration, Q₁₀ coefficient, spruce forests
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17333691

A special role in the carbon cycle belongs to emission of CO₂, which is formed mainly due to the respiration of microorganisms that decompose dead organic matter, and the respiration of plant roots. It should be noted that the ecosystem/soil type, season of the year, and differences between study years have a significant influence on efflux CO₂ from soils. The processes of mineralization and humification in soils occur simultaneously. Therefore, the organic soil matter is both the material for the complete decomposition and emission of CO₂ into the atmosphere, and the source of organic components for the synthesis of humic acids. The aim of the study is to characterize the soil respiration of the middle taiga herb-blueberry and sphagnum spruce forests growing on the Mezensko-Vychegodskaya plains of the Komi Republic.

The work was carried out in the middle taiga subzone of the Komi Republic on the territory of the Lyalsky test site of the Institute of Biology of Komi Science Centre of the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences. The study involved herb-blueberry spruce forests on Glossic Stagnic Retisol and sphagnum spruce forests on Histic Stagnic Retisol. Soil respiration measurements were carried out during May–October 2023–2024 using an LI-8100 gas analyzer (LI COR, United States) with a dark soil chamber with a diameter of 20 cm. At the same time, the temperature at a depth of 10 cm and moisture in a layer of 0–5 cm were determined using sensors included with the device. Automatic data loggers HOBO (Onset, United States) were used for continuous hourly recording of soil temperature at the study sites.

In the mid-taiga spruce forests, a “classic” course of the soil respiration curve was observed during the warm period with maximum values in July and August. In a spruce forest on automorphic soil, average monthly values varied in 2023 from 2.6 to 5.4 gCm²/day, in 2024 they varied from 1.3 to 5.1 gCm²/day. Soil respiration of the sphagnum community was 1.2–2.9 times lower ($p_t < 0.05$) in all months except July 2023, when fluxes were comparable ($p_t = 0.126$). Using the soil temperature dynamics at a depth of 10 cm as a predictor, it was calculated that during the warm period, 591–596 gCm² were released into the atmosphere from the surface of the Glossic Stagnic Retisol and 380–421 gCm² from the Histic Stagnic Retisol. The intensity of the C–CO₂ flux during the years of research is comparable with a slightly higher value in 2023. The summer months account for the majority (62–68%) of the warm period C–CO₂ flux. Favorable soil moisture conditions, as well as the presence of a greater number of deciduous species producing easily decomposable litter, caused higher (1.4–1.6 times) losses of C–CO₂ from typical podzolic soil. Soil temperature had a positive effect on emission of CO₂ ($R^2=0.54–0.87$), while soil moisture had a negative effect ($R^2=0.21–0.40$). In the forest on Histic Stagnic Retisol soil, Q₁₀ was higher due to less favorable soil moisture conditions.

The work was carried out Most Important Innovative Project of National Importance “Development of a system of ground-based and remote monitoring of carbon pools and greenhouse gas flows on the territory of the Russian Federation, ensuring the creation of a system for recording data on the flows of climate-active substances and the carbon budget in forests and other terrestrial ecological systems” and topic of the state assignment of the Institute of Biology of Komi Science Centre of the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences (Reg. № 125020501547-8).

Soil organic matter and carbon stocks in soils on binary sediments

Lapteva E.¹, Likhanova I.¹, Skrebenkov E.^{1,2}, Bondarenko N.¹, Smotrina Yu.^{1,2}, Shchanov V.¹

¹Institute of Biology Komi SC UrD RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia, lapteva@ib.komisc.ru

²Pitirim Sorokin Syktyvkar State University, Syktyvkar, Russia

Keywords: middle taiga, podzolic soils, organic horizons, carbon stocks, litter stocks
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17334443

Measurement of SOM content and stocks is one of the most important characteristics of soil organic matter in terrestrial ecosystems. Considering that soils on two-membered deposits are quite widespread in the territory of the European North-East (including the territory of the Komi Republic), this work assesses the SOC stocks in organogenic horizons and in the soil profile as a whole in this type of soil, developed in different conditions of hydromorphism and under different types of forest.

The study focused on soils from the Lyalsky test site (62°15' N, 50°40' E). The site was created in the Komi Republic as part of the Unified National System for Monitoring Climate-Active Substances project. Within the testing area, 30 sample plots (SP) have been established, which are conditionally assigned to 6 groups of forest types: 1 – small-leaved herbaceous, dwarf shrub, and herbaceous-dwarf shrub birch and aspen forests; 2 – herbaceous spruce forests; 3 – dwarf shrub-green moss spruce forests, including dwarf shrub-long-moss spruce forests; 4 – dwarf shrub-sphagnum spruce forests, including grass-sphagnum spruce forests; 5 – dwarf shrub-green moss pine forests; 6 – dwarf shrub-sphagnum pine forests. The soil cover of the considered SPs is represented by various types and subtypes of alfehumus and eluvial soils. When assessing SOC stocks, subhorizons of forest litter with a SOC content of > 20% were classified as organogenic horizons; with a SOC content of < 20%, they were classified as organo-mineral and taken into account in the composition of the mineral part of the profile.

The morphological and chemical characteristics of soil organic matter (SOM) vary widely in soils on binary deposits (sands underlain by loams). This is due to differences in the structure of the vegetation cover, the composition of plant litter, moisture conditions, the nature of the underlying rocks, topography, and microbiota activity.

Organogenic horizons in soils of small-leaved forests, as well as grassy and green moss spruce forests, are characterized by relatively thin (5–6 cm) organic horizons, with stocks ranging from 37–54 t/ha. Green moss pine forests accumulate thicker (12 cm) organic matter, with reserves of up to 73 t/ha. Increasing soil moisture in sphagnum forest types contributes to an increase in the organic matter thickness to 15–17 cm, and reserves to 85–105 t/ha. An assessment of carbon stocks in organogenic horizons and a meter-thick soil profile revealed that carbon stocks in organic horizons vary depending on forest type, ranging from 12.8 ± 2.1 to 64.0 ± 7.9 t/ha, while in the meter-thick soil profile, they range from 78.3 ± 7.0 to 133.9 ± 14.0 t/ha. Of the total organic carbon stocks accumulated in the meter-thick soil profile, organic horizons account for up to 15–40% in automorphic soils and up to 49% in semihydromorphic soils.

In soils of forest communities occupying automorphic relief positions, the thickness and reserves of organic matter decrease in the order near-trunk elevation → under-crown space → inter-crown space. In sphagnum forest types, the opposite trend is observed, which may be due to the drainage influence of trees and microrelief features.

The work was supported by the Unified National Monitoring System for Climatically Active Substances, the Most Significant Innovation Project of State Importance and by the project no. 125021201993-3 “Microbial Communities of the Northern Ecosystems, Their Biotechnological Potential and Technologies for Its Realization”.

Effect of the nature of humic substances and ionic strength on the stabilization of colloidal bentonite

Lasareva E.V., Parfenova A.M.

Lomonosov Moscow State University, Moscow, Russia, elasareva@yandex.ru

Keywords: humic substances, aggregative stability, coagulation, colloidal bentonite
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17334492

The transport of the colloidal component of river runoff into the marine environment has been poorly studied, although it directly depends on the stability of dispersed systems with increasing salinity. The study of the aggregative stability of clay colloids, which are one of the components of river waters, is important not only as investigation of river water dynamic but also for the study of water treatment conditions. Previously, we demonstrated the ability of humic acids (HA) to stabilize bentonite colloids with increasing salinity (ionic strength) of water in an experiment simulating the mixing zone of river and seawater [1]. The aim of this work was to evaluate the influence of different HA on the stability of colloidal bentonite (CB) at different ionic strength of their solutions.

Bentonite (Oglanli deposit, Tajikistan, fraction $<1 \mu\text{m} >50\%$) was used as a model clay mineral. Coal humic acids (HA-Pow) (Powhumus, Germany), Sakhalinsky humate (SH) (Sakhalinsky Humates, Russia) and Lignohumate (LH) (St. Petersburg, Russia) were used as HA samples.

CB was obtained from the top layer of the solution after settling the bentonite suspension (2 g/L) for 10 days at room temperature (CB particle size is 180-200 nm, zeta potencial -37 mV). Modification of clay particles by HA (10 mg/l) was carried out by their adsorption on clays for 5 days at room temperature. The turbidity of the samples, as a measure of the colloidal stability, was studied with the use of a HI 98713-02 turbidimeter (Hanna, Romania). Drop shape analysis was used for determining the contact angle of the drop on the glass plates as the measure of hydrophilicity of HA. The parameters for comparing the stability of the dispersed system were the time during which the system does not react to the presence of salt or the concentration of salt that causes coagulation over a certain period of time.

It was shown, that as the hydrophilicity of HA increases (determined by the decrease in the contact angle of a water drop on the glass plate modified with HA), their ability to stabilize CB increases. Thus, coagulation of CB modified with SH at a salinity of 17 ‰ occurs only after 60 minutes, whereas the effect of HA-Pow under the same conditions is noticeable after 20 minutes. At the same time the contact angle for SH does not change significantly with increasing HA concentration having value near 28° , whereas for HA-Pow it increases from 28° to 34° , passing through a maximum of 46° . Thus, CB stabilization in mixing zones is influenced not only by the type of HA, but also by their concentration.

Acknowledge. The authors thank colleagues from the Organic Chemistry Department of Lomonosov Moscow State University for providing humic substances preparations.

The work was performed in the framework of the State Assignment "Colloidal Chemistry", number CITIS 121031300084-1

References

1. Lasareva, E.V.; Parfenova, A.M. Influence of Organic Matter on the Transport of Mineral Colloids in the River-Sea Transition Zone. Chapter 5. In *Oceanography - Relationships of the Oceans with the Continents, Their Biodiversity and the Atmosphere*, Leonel, P., Pardal, M.A.; IntechOpen: London, Great Britain, 2024; pp. 97-116, <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.104007>

Specificity of soil humus substances at ash dumps

Nekrasova O., Uchaev A.

Institute of Natural Sciences and Mathematics, Ural Federal University, Yekaterinburg, Russia,
o_nekr@mail.ru

Keywords: fly ash, Technosols, humic acids, fulvic acids, southern taiga
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17334529

Data on the composition of soil humus substances formed on the surface of ash dumps is extremely scarce, though they occupy large areas in some regions of Russia and other countries. The fly ash is a specific technogenic substrate and it may differ from rocks in properties that are significant for its synthesis and accumulation.

At the same time, establishing the specifics of soil humus formed on a technogenic substrate can help to understand the features of humus formation under specific local conditions, and as a result, identify the contribution of individual factors to the global process of carbon deposition by soils. This information can also help address issues related to restoring disturbed lands.

This study aims to establish the specifics of humus substances in soils formed on unreclaimed areas of 50-60-year-old ash dumps under meadow and forest communities in the southern taiga conditions of the Middle Urals (using the ash dumps of the Verkhnetagilsky and Sredneuralsky power plants as an example). The composition of humus was studied according to [1].

It was found that the humus substances in Technosols with a pH value of <7.0, formed under mixed aspen-birch forests on both ash dumps and in a meadow community dominated by cereals and forbs at the Sredneuralsky ash dump, are characterized by a significantly lower content of extractable substances - humic acids (HA) and fulvic acids (FA) and, accordingly, a higher proportion of humins compared to background sod-podzolic soils.

At the same time, the proportion of individual fractions of humic and fulvic acids in these soils is similar: free and bound with mobile sesquioxides humic acids (HA1) and associated with them fulvic acids (FA1) predominate, and the values of the integrated humus index (Cha:Cfa) do not exceed 1.

In contrast to that, the humus substances of the meadow area Technosols at Verkhnetagilsky ash dump with a pH value >7.0 differ from background soils in all major parameters. They have a high proportion of extractable humus acids, with humic acids prevailing over fulvic acids in the upper horizons and bounded with calcium HA dominating in the fractional composition of humic acids.

Therefore, the characteristics of ash material influence the formation of humus in soils of ash dumps. In slightly alkaline conditions, more humic substances are formed with an increased proportion of humic acids, dominated by related with calcium humic acids. This indicates a more intense incorporation of calcium into the biological cycle. In acidic conditions, which bring soil formation closer to that of sod-podzolic soils, humus formation on ash dumps follows a pattern similar to that found in southern taiga soils.

Acknowledgements. The work was performed within the framework of the state assignment of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education (topic No. FEUZ-2024-0011).

References

1. Ponomareva VV, Plotnikova TA. Metodicheskiye ukazaniya po opredeleniyu sodержaniya i sostava gumusa v pochvakh [Guidelines for Determining the Content and Composition of Humus in Soils]. Leningrad: Nauka Publ.; 1975. 106 p.

Is there a relationship between the carbon content of microbial biomass and soil organic matter parameters in clear-cut soils of the taiga zone?

Perminova E., Lapteva E.

Institute of Biology Komi SC UrD RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia, perminova@ib.komisc.ru

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17334560

Microbial biomass is an important component of soil organic matter. Their parameters can be good indicators of soil quality and the quality of the natural environment. This study examines the relationship between soil microbial community parameters and soil organic matter characteristics in forest ecosystems transformed by clear-cutting. The research was conducted in the middle taiga subzone of the European North-East of Russia (Komi Republic). The key plots are represented by a native bilberry-green moss spruce forest (plot KE) and three derivative phytocenoses formed after clear-cutting: site PP 0 (clear-cut in 2017-2018), PP 2 (2001-2002), and PP 3 (1969-1970). The total carbon content (TOC) in the samples was assessed using a CHNS-O analyzer, and the carbon content of organic compounds in aqueous extracts (WSOC) was determined using the high-temperature catalytic oxidation method using a VCPH TOC analyzer [3] at the Collective Use Center «Chromatography» of the Institute of Biology of the Komi Scientific Center of the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences. Microbial community parameters (basal respiration and microbial biomass carbon) were determined using the substrate-induced respiration (SIR) method.

As a result of the research conducted, the following was established:

1) Carbon stocks in the organogenic horizon of the podzolic soil of the plot KE are 2.4 ± 0.5 kg/m², in the eluvial horizon (top 5 cm) – 1.83 ± 0.28 kg/m². In the first years after clear-cutting, carbon stocks in the upper horizons increase by 1.4-2.2 times. During natural reforestation, C reserves gradually decrease, and in plot PP 3 (50 years after clear-cutting), carbon stocks in the organogenic horizons are 1.9-3.4 times lower than in plot KE, and in the mineral horizons, they are 1.5-2.7 times lower.

2) In the soil of plot KE, the share of water-soluble carbon (WSOC) in the TOC pool is 1.8-1.9%. In plot PP 0, the share of S_{vob} decreases to 1.3%, but during further natural reforestation, the share of WSOC increases to 2.1% (PP2) and 2.3% (PP3). In the eluvial horizons, the share of WSOC decreases by 1.7-2.2 times.

3) The minimum values of microbial biomass carbon (C_{mic}) were recorded in the organogenic soil horizons at plots PP 0 and PP 2 (2129-5058 µg C/g soil). At plots KE and PP 3, C_{mic} was 7030 and 8523 µg C/g soil, respectively. In the eluvial horizons of all soils, C_{mic} values decreased by an order of magnitude and averaged 268.4 (KE), 438.6 (PP 0), 481.7 (PP 2), and 644.5 (PP 3) µg C/g soil.

4) The maximum values of basal respiration (BR) were established in the organogenic horizons of the KE plot (40.9 µg C-CO₂ / g of soil), in the PP 0, PP 2 and PP 3 plots this indicator averaged 19.5, 28.3 and 32.9 µg C-CO₂ / g of soil, respectively. In the mineral horizons, a trend of increasing BR is observed in the direction: KE → PP 2 → PP 3 → PP 0.

5) The parameter that most closely correlates with the characteristics of microbial communities is the content and stocks of WSOC – the relationship between WSOC and C_{mic} is characterized by the value $r = 0.76$ ($p = 0.95$), between WSOC and BD – $r = 0.67$. In the eluvial horizons of the studied podzolic soils, correlation dependencies between the parameters of microbial communities and the parameters of soil organic matter were not revealed.

The work was supported by the Institute of Biology, project no. 125021201993-3 “Microbial Communities of the Northern Ecosystems, Their Biotechnological Potential and Technologies for Its Realization”.

Comparative analysis of optical data from Solzan landfill storage cards

Petrov K.V.¹, Khreptugova A.N.¹, Larionov K.S.¹, Vladimirov S.A.¹, Pechnikova G.S.¹, Zhurba V.S.¹, Perminova I.V.¹

¹Lomonosov Moscow State University, Department of Chemistry, Moscow, Russia
mnbv21228@mail.ru

Keywords: sludge lignin, Baikalsk pulp and paper mill, mass-spectrometry, fluorescence
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17338166

Operational quality control of the aquatic environment in industrial waste storage areas is a critically important task. The above-sludge waters of the Baikalsk Pulp and Paper Mill storage cards, which pose a potential threat to the Baikalsk ecosystem in the event of a violation of the integrity of the enclosing dams, were chosen as the object of the study [1]. Optical methods are used in this study to quickly and efficiently analyze the composition of dissolved organic matter (DOM). Their effectiveness is based on the correlation between the absorption and fluorescent properties of DOM and its molecular characteristics. The aim of the work is to evaluate the spatial differentiation of the parameters of the DOM in above-sludge storage waters in order to identify statistically significant trends in their differences.

The dataset was created on the basis of 82 samples of above-sludge waters analyzed using fluorescence spectroscopy and UV-visible spectrometry. Absorption and excitation-emission matrix (EEM) spectra were used to calculate optical descriptors. Fluorescence emission band asymmetry, indicative of protein fluorescence contribution, was calculated as the ratio of integrated intensities at 350 nm excitation in the blue (420-460 nm) and red (550-600 nm) spectral regions. Humic and fluorescent indices were also calculated for fluorescence. Using data on the organic carbon content, the SUVA parameter characterizing the aromaticity of the DOM was calculated.

The purpose of the study is to establish patterns of spatial distribution of key characteristics (optical descriptors: Asm_{350} , $SUVA_{254}$, FI, HI) between different storage cards. To identify trends, the cluster analysis method is used to group storage cards according to similar characteristics. Statistical data processing was performed, including ANOVA analysis of variance to test the hypothesis of the significance of differences between the average values of indicators in different maps. Spatial trends were visualized and analyzed by constructing cartographic models (maps of isolines) of the distribution of descriptors. In order to confirm the results obtained by optical methods, the Fourier transform mass spectrometry (FT-ICR MS) method was applied.

It was found that in lignin storage cards (2 and 3) there is a strong correlation ($r = 0.9 - 1$) of spectral asymmetry Asm_{350} with the fluorescent index FI, and a very strong inverse correlation ($r = -0.85 - -0.94$) of Asm_{350} and FI with the humic index HI, whereas for ash storage cards such a correlation is not observed. The fourth storage card is unique in its correlation of the humic index with the asymmetry of the spectrum ($r = 0.8$), while for the remaining cards this value is less than zero ($r = -0.5 - -0.9$).

Acknowledgments. This work was supported by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Russian Federation, grant No. 075-15-2024-533. The study was performed using the equipment of "Human Proteome" Core Facilities of the Institute of Biomedical Chemistry (Russia).

References

[1] Chebykin, E., Dambinov, Yu., Suturin, A. (2020). Multi-element analysis of above-sludge waters in the accumulation cells of Baikalsk pulp and paper mill for territory remediation strategy choosing. *Water and Ecology*. 25. 67-80. 10.23968/2305-3488.2020.25.4.67-80.

Post-agrogenic dynamics of molecular composition of humic acids in North-West Russia

Polyakov V., Abakumov E.

Department of Applied ecology, Saint-Petersburg state university, University Embankment, 7/9, Saint-Petersburg, Russia, 199034; v.polyakov@spbu.ru

Keywords: ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy; boreal zone; fallow state; Retisol; Podzol.
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17338230

Today, a significant amount of land has transitioned from agricultural use to fallow state. These lands are undergoing processes such as shrub encroachment, waterlogging, and afforestation, which lead to degradation and the loss of carbon from soils. According to estimates by N. Ramankutty and J. Foley [1], up to $1.5 \cdot 10^6$ hectares of arable land have been lost from agricultural use. The majority of these lands are located in economically developed countries in Eastern Europe, Southeast Asia, as well as post-Soviet countries [2]. While it is known that this shift alters soil carbon stocks, the dynamics of the molecular composition of soil organic matter (SOM), which determines its long-term stability, remain poorly understood. The critical question is whether the natural restoration on fallow lands leads to the formation of stable, recalcitrant organic matter or to the accumulation of a labile carbon pool vulnerable to degradation, with major implications for carbon sequestration strategies and land management. Thus, this study aims to investigate the dynamics of the molecular composition of HAs extracted from post-agrogenic soils of the taiga zone of North-West Russia. To analyze the carbon state of soils on fallow lands in the North-West of Russia, a calculation of the content and stock of carbon in the soils was carried out, as well as elemental and molecular composition of humic acids (HAs) extracted from the soils was performed. To investigate the dynamics of molecular composition, the ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy method was used.

The analysis confirmed that soil carbon stocks decrease initially after abandonment but recover with time, approaching background levels as organic litter (Oi) horizons form. However, the molecular investigation revealed a counterintuitive trend: the elemental and structural composition of HAs showed a decrease in the content of stable aromatic carbon fragments and an increase in labile aliphatic fragments with increasing fallow age. HAs from fallow soils exhibited higher oxidation levels (higher O/C ratios) compared to those from native soils. The most mature and stable molecular structures were identified not in the oldest fallows, but in the mineral horizons of the background native ecosystems. The study concludes that while post-agrogenic succession leads to the accumulation of organic carbon, it primarily results in the formation of a labile carbon pool prone to biodegradation rather than a stable one. The molecular destabilization of HAs over time indicates that prolonged fallow state may not ensure long-term carbon sequestration and could even increase the ecosystem's vulnerability to carbon loss upon disturbance. These findings highlight the need for strategic management of fallow lands, suggesting that recultivation efforts should prioritize recently abandoned areas where the labile carbon pool is smaller, to minimize potential carbon emissions.

Acknowledgements. This work was supported by the Russian Scientific Foundation in accordance with agreement from 20.04.2023 № 23-16-20003 and Saint-Petersburg Scientific Foundation in accordance with agreement from 05.05.2023 № 23-16-20003.

References

1. Ramankutty N., Foley J.A. Estimating historical changes in global land cover: Croplands from 1700 to 1992. *Global Biogeochem. Cycles* 1999, Vol.13(4), P. 997-1027.
2. Kalinina O., Cherkinsky A., Chertov O., Goryachkin S., Kurganova I., Lopes de Gerenyu V., Lyuri D., Kuzyakov Y., Giani L. Post-agricultural restoration: Implications for dynamics of soil organic matter pools. *Catena* 2019, Vol. 181, ID 104096.

The role of laccase in synthesis and degradation of humic substances

Zavarzina A.

Faculty of Soil Science, Moscow State University, Moscow, Russia

Keywords: humic acids, free-radical reactions, degradation, carbon cycle

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17338253

Soil organic matter (SOM) is the largest reservoir of organic carbon in terrestrial ecosystems. Up to 80% of SOM is represented by alkali-extractable compounds, defined as humic substances (HS). The pathways of their formation and decomposition are not fully understood yet. It is believed that it is largely an oxidative catalytic process with extracellular microbial phenoloxidases and peroxidases playing an important role in transformation of phenolic compounds – aromatic constituents and precursors of HS. Free radicals produced during phenolic substrates oxidation undergo spontaneous coupling or initiate depolymerization reactions. However, occurrence of free radical reactions under soil conditions, their role in the formation and stabilization of SOM and biochemical stability of high molecular weight humic components are still under the discussion. Here we show the importance of free-radical reactions catalyzed by laccase in synthesis, stabilization and transformation of humic components of SOM.

Laccase (benzene diol: oxidoreductase, EC 1.10.3.2) is one of the most common phenoloxidases in soils. It is produced by fungi and bacteria and catalyzes oxidation of phenolic substrates and aromatic amines by molecular oxygen which is reduced to water. Depending on the difference of redox potentials of an enzyme and a substrate, laccase can catalyze condensation and/or depolymerization reactions thus playing bifunctional role in synthesis and degradation of SOM. It occurs as two-domain (2D) and three-domain (3D) proteins. The 2D laccases are known exclusively in bacteria and catalyze substrate oxidation at alkaline pH values (8-9), while 3D laccases occur in both fungi and bacteria and catalyze substrate oxidation at acidic-neutral pH values (4-7). Therefore, two forms of laccase complement each other over a wide pH range during transformation of phenolic substrates. We developed a method to disentangle the 3D and 2D laccase-like oxidative activities in soils [1] and show that activities of both forms of laccase are comparable in organic and inorganic soil horizons. The average laccase activity was 0.17 U g^{-1} , peaking up to 1.2 U g^{-1} in the litter soil horizons and decreasing with soil depth to $0.01\text{--}0.37 \text{ U g}^{-1}$. Using naturally occurring values of laccase activities we studied the role of 3D laccase in binding and stabilization of lignin-derived phenolic acids on mineral phases at low substrate concentrations. Laccase enhanced phenolics binding by 2-3 times thus playing important role in C_{org} stabilization. We show that at low concentrations of phenolic monomers (0.01 mM) and flow-through conditions oxidative coupling reactions result in formation of fulvic-like compounds. High molecular compounds are formed at high substrate concentrations ($>2 \text{ mM}$) and under static conditions but are unstable when not bound to mineral soil phases, being depolymerized by laccase to low molecular weight fractions. 2D laccases catalyze only polymerization reactions of humic components thus playing important role in molecular stabilization of SOM. Preservation and enhancement of the natural level of laccase activity in soils, the introduction of laccase preparations in immobilized form into soils may be a promising approach to enhance humification as well as sequestration potential of soils.

Acknowledgements. The work has been supported by Russian Science Foundation grant 23-14-00152.

References.

1. Zavarzina A.G., Kulikova N.A., Trubitsina L.I., Belova O.V., Pyatova M.I., Danilin I.V., Pogozhev P.E., Kuzyakov Y., Lisov A.V. Soil Biology and Biochemistry, 2025, V. 208, p. 1-12.

3. The use of humic substances and plant raw materials in nature conservation and biomedical technologies

The detoxification potential of activated peat hydrosol towards cadmium ions

Alferova V.S.¹, Kosolapova N.I.¹, Nevedrov N.P.¹

¹Kursk State University, Kursk, Russia, viktoriyaa.ermakova@yandex.ru

Keywords: activated peat hydrosol, cadmium ions, detoxification

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17338295

To enhance the sorption capacity of soils incapable of retaining pollutants, materials with pronounced sorbent properties and high affinity for the soil environment are used [1]. A preparation based on activated peat hydrosol, produced by ultrasonic cavitation dispersion of peat raw material in an aqueous medium, can be considered as such a promising soil sorbent.

The aim of the study was to evaluate the sorption properties of activated peat and compare its efficacy with that of other materials (activated carbon and lignin) used as soil sorbents.

Sorption was carried out from model systems simulating soil solution (a 0.9% NaCl solution, the pH of which was adjusted to 6.7 using sodium bicarbonate).

As part of the study on the thermodynamic parameters of cadmium ion sorption by activated peat and the selected sorbents, sorption isotherms were constructed. The obtained data were processed using the Langmuir mathematical model. [2] The sorption capacity (a_m) of the activated peat hydrosol preparation, activated carbon, and lignin for Cd^{2+} was 151.5 mg/g, 111.1 mg/g, and 107.5 mg/g, respectively.

The kinetics of cadmium ion (Cd^{2+}) sorption on activated peat hydrosol and the comparison preparations were studied using the limited volume solution method with the construction of kinetic curves. The rate constant of the sorption process for the activated peat hydrosol preparation, activated carbon, and lignin was $1.7 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ g} \cdot \text{mg}^{-1} \cdot \text{min}^{-1/2}$, $1.0 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ g} \cdot \text{mg}^{-1} \cdot \text{min}^{-1/2}$, and $1.1 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ g} \cdot \text{mg}^{-1} \cdot \text{min}^{-1/2}$, respectively.

Based on the results obtained, it can be concluded that preparations based on activated peat hydrosol have the highest sorption capacity for Cd^{2+} ions. Consequently, their application contributes to increasing the sorption capacity of soils and better "capturing" of soil pollutants, preventing their further movement through biosystems.

References:

1. Gorbunova N.S., Gromovik A.I., Cherepukhina I.V., Terentyeva Yu.Yu. // Sorption processes in soils. Issues of study and current state of the problem. 2021. Vol. 21. №. 2. Pp. 265-275.

2. Osipova E.A. // News of higher educational institutions. Chemistry and chemical technology. 2023. Vol. 6. №. 9. Pp. 65-70.

The influence of humic preparations on soil fertility and the yield of pea (*Pisum sativum* L.)

Bezuglova O.^{1,2}, Gorovtsov A.^{1,2}, Lychman V.², Polienko E.²

¹Southern federal university, Rostov-on-Don, Russia, lola314@mail.ru

²Federal Rostov Agrarian Scientific Center, settl. Rassvet, Russia

Keywords: humic preparations, *Pisum sativum*

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17338452

In a field experiment conducted during 2021–2023, the effects of the humic preparations "BIO-Don" and "Potassium Humate" on the yield of pea and soil fertility indicators were studied. The humic preparations were applied foliarly during the pod formation period as a tank mixture with an insecticide. Statistical processing and principal component analysis were performed using STATISTICA 12 software.

It was established that humic preparations affect the abundance of rhizosphere microorganisms differently. While BIO-Don promotes the growth of heterotrophs and decreases the activity of bacteria that grow on mineral forms of nitrogen, Potassium Humate promotes the growth of micromycetes more strongly. An increase in the number of microorganisms in the rhizosphere zone of plants indicates their activation by root exudates of plants treated with humic preparations, which in turn affects the water stability of structural aggregates and the availability of nutrients. Principal component analysis showed that yield correlates with the quantity of available phosphorus and potassium, water stability of the structure, and the number of micromycetes in the soil.

The correlation is considered strong. Presumably, the role of micromycetes in this association is due to their ability to secrete organic acids into the environment, which in turn promotes the conversion of sparingly soluble phosphates into available forms. The possibility of such a conversion following treatment of plants with humic preparations was demonstrated in study [1]. Micromycetes also contribute to the maceration of dead organic tissues and the decomposition of organic substances, thereby influencing soil structure formation [2].

The quantity of actinomycetes and bacteria absorbing organic and mineral nitrogen in the rhizosphere zone affects soil fertility indicators, especially, nitrate nitrogen content. The correlation with ammonium nitrogen is weaker, possibly due to its stronger association with the soil adsorption complex. The correlation of humus content with the indicated parameters is weaker and likely more indirect, as this parameter is more stable; nonetheless, a moderate correlation was shown.

Thus, foliar treatment with humic preparations contributes to an increase in the yield of peas, which is primarily due to the conversion of poorly available forms of phosphorus into available ones and the improvement of the structural state of the soil. Micromycetes of the rhizosphere zone play a leading role in these processes.

References

1. Dubinina M. N., Bezuglova O. S. The effect of a humic preparation on the fractional-group composition of phosphates in ordinary carbonate chernozem // Proceedings of Higher Education Institutions. North Caucasus Region. Natural Sciences. 2022. No. 1 (213). P. 38–48.

2. Zinchenko M. K., Fedulova I. D., Sharkevich V. V. The complex of micromycetes and actinomycetes in agroecological monitoring of gray forest soil of agrolandscapes // Vladimirsky Zemledelets. 2019. No. 3(89). P. 15–19. DOI 10.24411/2225–2584–2019–10073.

Humification is a natural, nature-preserving technology that can be used in a closed-loop economy

Chukov S.N.

St. Petersburg State University, St. Petersburg, Russia

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17338506

The soil is considered as one of the largest carbon reservoirs in the biosphere (1,500 gigatons of carbon). Moreover, the main stable reservoir (at least hundreds and thousands of years) They are humic substances that are formed during the process of humification.

The popular concepts of "non-human" physical stabilization of soil organic matter, based mainly on the process of occluding undecayed organic residues with highly dispersed mineral particles, do not provide long-term stabilization of these residues. Their age, as a rule, does not exceed dozens of years. Whereas humic substances are much older. The process of humification leads to the formation of specific spatially distributed macromolecules of humic substances, which have significantly higher biothermodynamic stability. Even in conditions of an active biological cycle, their age in the soil is 1-3 thousand years.

Humification is the second largest process of transformation of organic matter after photosynthesis. The stability of humic substances as a reservoir of carbon sink is ensured by the biochemical stability of their molecular structure and their connection with the mineral matrix of the soil.

In 2021, IUPAC declared humification the No. 1 promising technology in solving the most important problems of mankind. Currently, humification is considered as an important component of a circular economy and as a promising decarbonization technology. The future belongs to humic substances obtained during the processes of humification of animal by-products, debris and other organic waste and the development of carbon negative eco-adaptive technologies within the framework of "green chemistry" and a closed-loop economy.

Artificial humification of organic waste and the development of carbon negative eco-adaptive technologies within the framework of "green chemistry" and a closed-loop economy is the most important task. Humification should be considered as an important component of the circular economy of a closed cycle

In Russia, this problem is being actively discussed and developed on the basis of the Federal Law regulating the processing of Organic Waste, which entered into force on March 1, 2023. On February 25, 2025, the Public Chamber of the Leningrad Region held a round table "Projects for the processing of organic waste for the purposes of recycling and/or obtaining secondary material resources." Baltic Agrochemical Union produces organic fertilizers using artificial humification technology followed by the addition of biological agents and enzymes. Baltorganic®

On March 27, 2025, the BRICS International Development Organization held an interregional intersectoral meeting on Sustainable Agriculture: a Vector for Fertility. It considered strategies for creating an eco-sustainable closed-loop model based on nature-like technologies and maintaining soil fertility.

On March 26-27, 2025, the VIII specialized conference "Organic Waste Management" was held in Moscow. It considered the use of organic and inorganic waste and fertilizers from them to regulate the fertility of agricultural land.

Chemical and biological activity of peats

Gileva D.A., Inisheva L.I., Porokhina E.V.

Tomsk State Pedagogical University, Tomsk, Russia, inisheva@mail.ru

Keywords: eutrophic peat, peat products, Western Siberia, enzymatic activity, organic matter, biological properties, correlation links
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17338537

The search for new raw materials of biologically active substances (**BAS**) of natural origin is an urgent task for the modern period. In this regard, peat is a relatively cheap and practically unlimited raw material base. However, the range of peat properties is quite wide and depends on the conditions of swamp formation, the depth of peat occurrence, and its botanical composition. Therefore, it is important to correctly select the necessary raw material base with specific requirements for the quality of peat and its reserves for the required products. The aim of the work was to study the composition of organic matter (**OM**), nitrogen peat, their enzymological activity, determine the correlation links between them and substantiate the criteria for the evaluation scale of the properties of eutrophic peat when choosing a raw material base for the production of BAS.

In the territory of Western Siberia, within the taiga and subtaiga regions, 140 samples of eutrophic peat belonging to 12 groups were selected. Each species of peat is represented of 6–19 samples, in which the botanical composition, degree of decomposition, ash content, fractional composition of nitrogen and organic matter, enzyme and microbiology activity were determined.

The following results were obtained. The content of humic acids (**HA**) in eutrophic peats increased in the following order: grass-moss – moss – wood – wood-grass, grass group. Peat groups differed significantly in the content of the HA-1 fraction. The moss group of peat stood out in particular with a low content of total nitrogen, its non-hydrolyzable fraction and a high content of easily hydrolyzable nitrogen, which determined the high mobility of nitrogen compounds. Among all the studied characteristics of the composition of peat OM, according to the correlation analysis, the following indicators are reliable: the sum of HA, lipids, carbohydrates and C:N ratio. This gives grounds to consider them as possible parameters for compiling an evaluation scale for selecting peats for the production of BAS.

A study of the enzymological and biological properties of eutrophic peats has established that an increase in the activity of invertase, protease, nitrate- and nitrite reductase, and polyphenoloxidase can be traced in the order: woody – woody-grass–grass. The calculation of the correlation coefficients between enzyme activity and parameters of other properties of eutrophic peats revealed that the greatest number of correlations were observed with fractions of peat OM and nitrogen, and to a lesser extent (r less than 0.7) with protease, nitrite reductase, peroxidase and parameters of microbiological properties of peats. In the process of analyzing correlation links, it was revealed that total and enzymatic catalase, polyphenoloxidase, and invertase can be controlling parameters of the enzymological state of eutrophic peats.

General conclusion: significant parameters of the evaluation scale of the properties of eutrophic peat for substantiating the choice of raw materials for the production of BAS are individual fractions of organic matter and nitrogen, total and enzymatic catalase, polyphenol oxidase, and invertase.

Acknowledgements. The study was carried out with the support of the state assignment, No. 5.7004.2017/64 and the Russian Science Foundation, grant No. 24-26-00161. <https://rscf.ru/project/24-26-00161/>.

The use of humic acids and their salts to extract gallium from the fly ash of brown coal thermal power plants

Karpova A.E.¹, Skripkina T.S.¹

¹Institute of Solid State Chemistry and Mechanochemistry SB RAS, Novosibirsk, Russia,
karpova.nas03@mail.ru

Keywords: humic acids, sodium humate, mechanochemical activation, fly ash, gallium
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17338739

The use of humic acids and their salts is of considerable interest for the development of environmentally sound technologies for the extraction of valuable metals from man-made waste. The use of natural and low-toxic reagents, which are humic substances, in the processing of fly ash from brown coal thermal power plants containing high concentrations of dispersed elements such as gallium, is a particularly promising area that minimizes the use of aggressive chemicals [1].

We used the fly ash from Novosibirsk CHPP-3 as a research object. This ash is characterized by a significant gallium content, up to 220 g/t. The main attention was paid to the study of the effectiveness of humic acids and their sodium salt (sodium humate) as complexing agents in the mechanochemical activation of ash in comparison with traditional reagents (EDTA, EDF, carbamide). The mechanochemical treatment was carried out on a planetary mill, which contributed to the destruction of the silicate matrix of the ash and increased the availability of the target elements [2].

The highest efficiency of converting gallium to a water-soluble form (81% of the total content) was achieved when the ash was mechanochemically activated using sodium humate. The ICP-MS data confirms this result. At the same time, the use of aggressive acids for the decomposition of the sample was not required. Unlike sodium humate, treatment with humic acids did not show a significant effect. Only one percent of gallium was extracted using this treatment method. This highlights the importance of the reagent shape. The results obtained demonstrate the prospects of using humic acid salts to create effective and environmentally friendly methods for extracting gallium from waste from brown coal thermal power plants.

The research was funded within the state assignment to ISSCM SB RAS (project №. FWUS-2024-0002).

References

1. Yudina L.I., Skripkina T.S., Shatskaya S.S. Mechanical Activation as a Stage of Coal Sample Preparation in the Analysis of Rare Earth Elements Content by Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry // *Curr Anal Chem*. Bentham Science Publishers, 2024. T. 20, № 1. C. 52–63.
2. Grabias-Blicharz E., Franus W. A critical review on mechanochemical processing of fly ash and fly ash-derived materials // *Science of The Total Environment*. 2023. T. 860. C. 160529.

Antioxidant activity of various fractions of humic substances in cosmetic compositions

Karpova Y.I.¹, Igumnova A.A.¹, Tikhonova T.V.¹

¹Mendeleev University of Chemical Technology of Russia, Moscow, Russia,
9162531545kar@gmail.com

Keywords: humic substances, antioxidant activity, cosmetic compositions
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17340786

Over the past two decades, interest in humic substances has expanded significantly and gone beyond the traditional study of soil organic matter; there is a demand for new humic-based products. This situation poses a challenge for science aimed at finding new areas of their application. For example, the use of humic substances in the cosmetic industry. Of particular interest is the use of humic substances as antioxidants, because scientists have opened a long time ago the presence of antioxidant properties in these compounds due to their structural features (the presence of a large number of quinoid, hydroxyl and carboxyl groups) [1].

The aim of this work was the study of antioxidant properties of humic substances in pure form and in cosmetic compositions. The object of the study was the fractions of humic and fulvic acids isolated from lowland peat.

To obtain humic substances, the alkaline extraction method was used. Humic acids were isolated by acidifying a sodium humate solution with a hydrochloric acid solution, and fulvic acids were isolated from the acidic filtrate after precipitation of humic acids, using adsorption of organic components on BAU-A carbon.

One of the possible parameters characterizing antioxidant capacity is the reducing capacity, defined as the amount of oxidizer reduced during interaction with a substance, normalized to its mass. To establish this parameter a spectrophotometric technique was used, which is based on the reaction of Fe (III) reduction to Fe (II) in the presence of humic substances. It was found that humic acids have the highest reducing capacity (more than the antioxidant comparison has) among humic substances, which may indicate greater antioxidant activity.

Emulsions were chosen as cosmetic compositions to introduce of antioxidants, since they are one of the most common cosmetic forms. In cosmetic emulsion compositions, humic acids also had greater antioxidant activity compared to fulvic acids and humic-fulvic complex.

Thus, humic substances are a promising antioxidant component for introduction into cosmetic emulsion forms. The obtained data can serve as a basis for the development of cosmetics and medicines.

References

1. Savchenko I.A., Korneeva I.N., Luksha E.A., Pasechnik K.K. (2019). Biological activity of humic substances: prospects and problems of their application in medicine. *MediAl Magazine*. 23, 54-60.

Lignins as promising plant polymers for biomedical applications

Kocheva L.S.¹, Karmanov A.P.², Raskosha O.V.²

¹Institute of Geology of the Komi Science Center UB RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia, karko07@mail.ru

²Institute of Biology of the Komi Science Center UB RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia, apk0948@yandex.ru

Keywords: lignins, chemical structure, physiological activity

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17340851

Lignin, one of the most complex and mysterious plant polymers in terms of chemical structure, has great potential for use in various fields of practical applications. In particular, they should be considered as promising raw materials for pharmaceuticals and biomedicine. Our research is aimed at studying the relationship between the structural and chemical features of lignins of various taxonomic origin and their physiological activity.

As a result of the conducted research, a hypothesis has been put forward about the key role of natural lignins in maintaining the balance of sex hormones in the mammalian body. Preparations based on natural and technical lignin are recommended for the prevention of age-related diseases caused by excessive levels of estrogens in the body.

Stable supramolecular complexes of citrus pectin and natural lignins and water-resistant colloidal particles lignin-PVP have been developed for the production of pharmaceutical preparations. It is concluded that lignins significantly contribute to the overall antioxidant activity of plant foods. Studying the geroprotective properties of natural lignins using the example of *Drosophila melanogaster* allowed us to propose a mechanism for the oncological and geroprotective effects of lignins.

The possibility of creating effective mycotoxin sorbents based on natural lignins and nanocarbon materials obtained by carbonation of lignocellulose raw materials was shown. Effective, including universal, lignin-containing sorbents of radionuclides (uranium, radium, thorium) for aqueous media were obtained.

In vivo experiments have shown the absence of toxic effects of lignin (based on the results of comparing body weight and index values of internal organs: brain, liver, heart, kidneys, testes and adrenal glands in experimental and control groups of animals). It was found that lignin has cytotoxic activity against HeLa, A549, and HT-29 tumor cells. The cytotoxic activity of natural lignin against cancer cells can be used in the practice of cancer treatment.

There was a significant increase in the potential (by increasing the yellow bodies of pregnancy in the ovary) and actual (number of embryos) fertility of female mice who consumed a lignin solution. The study of the gerontological properties of natural lignins in mice showed a positive effect on females; the differences between the males of the experimental and control groups were not statistically significant.

The effectiveness of the chronic action of lignin has been established with the manifestation of specificity depending on the sex of the animal in assessing motor activity, research behavior, speed of tentative research reaction, emotional reactivity, as well as anxiety ("T-shaped maze" tests).

The absence of a toxic effect with prolonged use of lignin by animals, the biological efficacy and the ability to modify radiation effects indicate the prospects for further research of natural lignin as an anti-radiation agent in both acute and chronic effects of ionizing radiation.

The conducted research opens up broad prospects for the creation of new lignin-containing preparates for biomedical applications.

The study was carried out at the expense of a grant from the Russian Science Foundation № 22-13-00196-P, <https://rscf.ru/en/project/22-13-00196/>.

Injection fluids based on humic acid-3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane complexes for immobilization of heavy metals

Kriuchkova D.S., Zhirkova A.M., Shestakov K.D., Larionov K.S., Volkov D.S., Konstantinov A.I., Perminova I.V.

Lomonosov Moscow State University, Department of Chemistry, Leninskie gory, 1-3, 119991 Moscow, Russia, dkriuchkova01205@gmail.com

Keywords: Humic substances, polyelectrolyte complexes, heavy metal, sorption; Cu; Ni; Pb
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17340909

The Arctic zone of the Russian Federation is subject to intense pollution by heavy metals (HM), primarily Ni, Cu and Pb, due to the activities of mining and metallurgical enterprises. High mobility of toxic metals creates risks for ecosystems and public health, which requires the development of effective and nature-like methods of immobilization. The objective of this research was preparation and characterization of new remedial agents based on polyelectrolyte complexes (PEC) of humic substances (HS) and 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES) for in situ installation of permeable reaction barriers (PRB) capable of intercepting and immobilizing HM in the contaminated aquifers.

Field sampling and comprehensive analysis of soils in the Norilsk region (ICP-OES) was carried out to determine the content of total and mobile forms of heavy metals with a use of nitric acid and ammonium acetate buffer extraction, respectively. Humic acids (HA) and fulvic acids (FA) were isolated from peats and permafrost of the Arctic zone. Their structural and group composition was studied using elemental analysis and NMR ^{13}C . The kinetics and isotherms of Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} sorption on native HA were studied. PECs with different stoichiometric ratios of APTES/HS were obtained. Their sorption kinetics and isotherms were studied on a model mineral carrier (silica gel). The efficiency of immobilized PECs under static and dynamic conditions for the sorption of Cu, Ni, and Pb was estimated.

It was found that the content of mobile forms of Ni and Cu in soils decreased exponentially with distance from the pollution source. A direct correlation was revealed between the content of mobile forms of HM and sulfur. The HA samples isolated from permafrost and peat demonstrated high sorption capacity with respect to Cu^{2+} (26–31 mg/g) and Ni^{2+} (14–19 mg/g). The sorption values dropped sharply at $\text{pH} < 4$. It was shown that APTES/HS PEC effectively sorbed on silica gel. The process could be described by pseudo-second-order kinetics. The maximum sorption capacity of PEC on the carrier was achieved at the APTES/HS ratio of 1:1. The further increase in APTES/HS ratio was accompanied by a drop of hydraulic permeability of mineral support. The immobilized PECs exhibited high efficiency in binding Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions. Under dynamic conditions (PRB modeling), it was shown that the introduction of PEC into a sandy soil model significantly increased its barrier function and slowed down substantially migration of model heavy metals.

It was concluded that a new approach to immobilization of heavy metals in the contaminated aquifers was successfully tested. It is based on injection of HS/APTES complexes into sandy contaminated grounds. The optimal composition for immobilization on a mineral matrix was a mass ratio of APTES/HS = 1:1. The proposed composition could be applied for in situ installation of PRB, which is an economically effective and environmentally safe alternative to traditional methods of groundwater treatment.

Acknowledgements. The study was carried out with a use of elemental analyzer (Perkin Elmer) at the facilities of the Analytical Center of Lomonosov Moscow State University. This research was partially supported by the State budgetary task 122040600057-3.

Investigation of the properties of humic acids of coal sludge from the Inta Mining and Processing Plant

Kuzmin D.V.¹, Burtsev I.N.¹, Brovarova O.V.²

¹Institute of Geology, Komi Science Centre of the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Syktyvkar, Russia, dvkuzmin@geo.komisc.ru

²Institute of Agrobiotechnology, Komi Science Centre of the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Syktyvkar, Russia

Keywords: coal sludge, humic substances

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17340972

Coal sludge is formed during the coal enrichment process. It contains both organic and mineral parts. The main problem in the processing of coal sludge is its high ash content (up to 80%) and fine dispersion (particle size is less than 1 mm).

The Inta coals include humic acids, are of a low carbonification degree. They are complex by petrographic composition. The coals are characterised by high ash content – 21.3–39% and low sulfur content – 2.17–3.35%. The study material was coal sludge taken from the sludge storage of the Kapitalnaya mine. Coal was extracted from a well down to a depth of 9 m. The samples were numbered from top to bottom, the sample core was divided into one-meter sections.

Humic acid salts were obtained by the Tyurin method [1]. The obtained sample of the humic acid (HA) preparation was identified for the content of hydroxyl (aliphatic and phenolic) and carboxyl groups, the content of which was 5.3%, 9.0% and 1.3%, respectively. Phenolic and carboxyl groups play the most significant role in aromatic structures, since they determine the ability of humic acids to bind to complexes with heavy metals [2]. This fact is of great interest of we consider the concentration of isotopes of uranium and other radionuclides. By our studies, humic acids (HA) extracted from coal sludge sorbed 47.6% of uranium from the solution with the sorption capacity 6.7 µg/g sorbent and the amount of bound uranium 3.5 µg/g sorbent.

To assess the effect of the humic preparation on agricultural plants, we performed phyto-testing with seeds of spring oats (*Avena sativa* L.). Phyto-testing was carried out in accordance with GOST 12038-84 [3].

By the obtained results, there are several different patterns of HA effects on the germination rate of spring oat seeds (*Avena sativa* L.). For example, low HA concentrations (0.005–0.025%) stimulated seed germination by 25–27% (germination energy). HA concentrations of more than 0.5% strongly inhibited the germination process of oat seeds. Germination in this case was no more than 50%. Thus, HAs can have either a stimulating effect on plants or act as a herbicide at high concentrations.

References

1. Orlov D.S., Grishina L.A. Practicum on humus chemistry. Moscow: Moscow University Publishing House, 1981. 272 p.
2. Aiken G.R., Hsu-Kim H., Ryan J.N. Influence of dissolved organic matter on the environmental fate of metals, nanoparticles, and colloids // Environ. Sci. Technol. 2011; 45: 3196–3201.
3. GOST 12038-84. Seeds of agricultural crops. Methods for determining germination. Date of introduction: July 1, 1986. Federal Agency for Technical Regulation. Official edition. Moscow: Standartinform, 2011. 30 p.

Processing of plant raw materials using closed-loop technologies to enhance soil quality and safety

Minkina T.M., Bauer T.V.

Southern Federal University, Rostov-on-Don, Russia, tminkina@mail.ru

Keywords: contamination soil remediation, biochar, heavy metal, sorbents

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17341095

Heavy metal (HM) contamination poses serious risks to soil ecosystems and human health, requiring cost-effective and sustainable remediation strategies. Traditional in-situ and ex-situ remediation techniques often involve costly and environmentally disruptive methods, such as surface capping, encapsulation, landfilling, soil flushing, electrokinetic extraction, solidification, vitrification, phytoremediation [1]. In contrast, HMs stabilization is generally considered as a cost-effective and environmentally friendly approach with rapid effects and at low cost prices [2]. The stabilization method is a remediation technology that uses various non-toxic materials to reduce the solubility of heavy metals in contaminated soils [3]. Among these materials, biochar is a carbon-rich green material that can be applied to stabilize HMs in soils. However, its adsorption performance is highly dependent on the pyrolysis conditions. This study evaluated the effects of pyrolysis conditions on the yield, structural properties, and adsorption capacity of biochar obtained wheat straw.

The pyrolysis of wheat straw was conducted by using a cylindrical reactor under a nitrogen environment to investigate the influence of various pyrolysis conditions on products yield distribution as well as physicochemical characteristics of produced biochars. Based on the obtained data, we identified the optimal pyrolysis conditions for achieving the highest porosity of biochar: temperature 700 °C, retention time 45 min, and heating rate 10 °C/min. The specific surface area of optimized biochar from wheat straw was 72 m²/g with a total pore volume of 0,046 cm³/g.

The efficiency of the developed biochar was investigated in pot experiments in both uncontaminated and metal-contaminated soil. Speciation and redistribution of heavy metals before and after the addition of sorbents to soil was investigated using BCR sequential extraction. Results from the study revealed that after the addition of biochar-based sorbents to soils the metal mobility of Cu, Pb, Zn, and Cd were all drastically reduced, and the effect of stabilization was shown by the transformation of metal from the more available fraction to the more stable oxidizable and residual fractions. The risk assessment code (RAC) decreased, and reduced partition index (IR) increased for all heavy metals with sorbent application, indicating an increase in their fixation strength in soils. X-ray diffraction analysis showed that the biochar effectively stabilized Pb, Cu and Zn in contaminated soils through precipitation processes. Overall, the study highlights the potential of biochar as an advanced soil amendment for sustainable remediation of heavy metal-contaminated soils.

Acknowledgements. The research was financially supported by the project of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of Russia (no. FENW-2024-0001).

References

1. Mulligan C., Yong R.N., Gibbs B.F. Remediation Technologies for Metal-Contaminated Soils and Groundwater: An Evaluation // Engineering Geology. 2001. V. 60. P. 193-207.
2. Khalid S., Shahid M., Niazi N.K., Murtaza B., Bibi I., Dumat C. A comparison of technologies for remediation of heavy metal contaminated soils. Journal of Geochemical Exploration. 2017. V. 182. P. 247-268.
3. Chen S.-B., Zhu Y.-G., Ma Y.-B., McKay G. Effect of bone char application on Pb bioavailability in a Pb-contaminated soil. Environmental Pollution. 2006. V. 139(3). P. 433-439.

Fuel oil contaminated ecosystems treatment using microbiological preparation in combination with dispersants based on humic substances and natural raw materials

Nazarov A.M.¹, Chetverikov S.P.², Davletshin T.K.³

¹Ufa State Petroleum Technical University, Ufa, Russia, nazarovam1501@gmail.com

²UFIMSKY Institute of Biology UFIC RAS, Ufa, Russia

³Aviakhim LLC, Ufa, Russia

Keywords: fuel oil, ecosystem cleaning, microbiological preparation, dispersants
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17341150

Fuel oil (FO) is a heavy fraction of oil with high viscosity and resistance to biodegradation, which, entering the ecosystem (soil, sand, water), disrupts its physico-chemical and biological characteristics, reduces water and air exchange, inhibits microflora and disrupts the circulation of substances. Large fuel oil spills: Norilsk in 2020 - 21 thousand tons into rivers and tundra soils; the Black Sea in 2024 - 4.5 thousand tons led to severe environmental consequences and economic damage amounting to hundreds of billions of rubles. Currently, special attention is being paid to biological methods of cleaning oil-polluted ecosystems based on the use of destructive microorganisms, in particular, bacteria of the genus *Rhodococcus* (including the BioOxOil biological preparation (BOO) based the strain *Rhodococcus degradans* H33) [1].

In the present work, laboratory experiments were conducted to study the effect of microbiological preparation in the presence of dispersants based on natural compounds (including humic substances) on reducing fuel oil concentrations in sand and water. In samples taken from oil-contaminated areas of the Black Sea coast sand (February 2025), the concentration of FO was 3; 5,0; 8,4; 15,5; 33,0 (g/kg). The experiment was carried out for 60 days for sand and 10 days for water. The microbiologics used were the preparation BOO and the microbiological comparison preparation «LenOil» (LO), sodium humate obtained from lignite (SH), thermally modified sapropel (SP), a dispersant based on sulfonated lignin (DSL), a dispersant based on methyl esters of coconut oil fatty acids (DCM), and It is also a dispersant based on inorganic salts, phosphates and carbonates (DIS). The effect of biologics and dispersants investigations on the FO concentration reducing in water were carried out at an initial fuel oil concentration of 3000 mg/l.

The efficiency increasing of fuel oil contaminated seawater purification was measured in the series:

DIS (35.4 %) < LO (57.3%) < BOO (71.2 %) < DSL (71.8 %) < DCM (76.4%) < LO + DIS (80.1%) < LO + DCM (86.3%) < LO + SH (87.3%) < SH (88.4 %) < BOO + DCM (88.5%) < BOO + DIS (90.1%) < LO + DSL (90.3%) < BO + SH (91.9%) < BO + SP (92.3%) < BO + DSL (92.7%).

Investigation of the effect of microbiologics in combination with dispersants on reducing the concentration of fuel oil in coastal sand samples have shown that for all variants, the effectiveness increases in the range of «LenOil» (21.5-49.2%) < «BioOxOil» (28.2-69.7%) < «BioOxOil» + DIS (34.9-72.5%) < «BioOxOil» + DSL (38.3-77.4%).

Thus, «BioOxOil», modified with a dispersant based on sulfonated lignin, showed the best efficiency for both water and sand - 92.7%. The performance of the «BioOxOil» preparation modified with a sapropel-based dispersant (containing a significant amount of humic substances) is slightly lower - the effectiveness is 92.3%, and sodium humate is 91.9%.

1. Patent №. 2759662 C2 Russian Federation, IPC C12N 1/20, C02F 3/34. Bacterial strain *Rhodococcus degradans* H33 ac-2901D - oil and petroleum products destructor : №. 2021121501 : application 07/19/2021 : published 11/16/2021 ; applicant AVIAKHIM Limited Liability Company.

Study of some biological effects of humic substances

Poloskov A.I.¹, Tovpeko D.V.¹, Yu Z.², Larionov K.S.², Soloviev D.A.^{1,3}, Mitiukov A.S.⁴,
Alexander-Sinclair E.I.³, Perminova I.V.², Glushakov R.I.¹

¹Kirov Military Medical Academy, Saint Petersburg, Russia, a.i.poloskov@gmail.com

²Lomonosov Moscow State University, Moscow, Russia

³Institute of Cytology Russian Academy of Science, Saint Petersburg, Russia

⁴Institute of Limnology Russian Academy of Sciences, Saint Petersburg, Russia

Keywords: humic substances, silver nanoparticles, antibacterial activity, cytotoxicity, hemocompatibility

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17341233

Humic substances have been shown to have various biological properties with high therapeutic potential. In this study, humic acids modified with silver nanoparticles (HA-Ag) and fulvic acids (FA) were tested for antibacterial activity, cytotoxicity and hemocompatibility.

Humic acids stabilized by silver nanoparticles and fulvic acids were found to have antibacterial activity against the methicillin-resistant strain of *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). The results in the table 1 show the antimicrobial activity of HA-Ag and FA.

Table 1. Antibacterial activity of HA-Ag and FA. Green indicates complete suppression of bacterial growth, and red indicates the absence of it

HA, mg/L	0	20	40	60	80	100	200		FA, mg/L	0	20	40	60	80	100	200
Ag, µg ml ⁻¹	0	4.7	14.7	22.0	29.4	36.7	73.5									

The presence of FA in the nutrient media did not have a significant toxic effect on DF cultured in them for 2 days: cell viability was comparable to the control or close to it. The content of HA-Ag in the nutrient medium in all studied concentrations had a weakly expressed cytotoxic effect on DF cultured in them for 2 days: cell viability was lower than the control, but higher than 80%.

An assessment of the hemocompatibility of FA and HA-Ag was carried out. It was established that FA do not have hemolytic activity. HA-Ag with concentrations below 40 mg/L do not have hemolytic activity. Concentrations from 60 to 100 mg/L have a weak hemolytic activity. Concentration 200 mg/L has a high hemolytic activity (table 2).

Table 2. Hemolytic activity of HA-Ag and FA. Green indicates the absence of hemolytic activity, yellow indicates weak hemolytic activity, and red indicates high hemolytic activity

HA, mg/L	0	20	40	60	80	100	200		FA, mg/L	0	20	40	60	80	100	200
Ag, µg ml ⁻¹	0	7.4	14.7	22.0	29.4	36.7	73.5									

References

1. Humic Polyelectrolytes Facilitate Rapid Microwave Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles Suitable for Wound-Healing Applications / Yu. Zhang, K. S. Larionov, S. Zhang [et al.] // Polymers. 2024. Vol. 16, No. 5. P. 587.

2. Al-Zyoud W., Haddadin D., Hasan S.A., Jaradat H., Kanoun O. Biocompatibility Testing for Implants: A Novel Tool for Selection and Characterization. Materials. 2023; 16(21):6881.

3. Weber M., Steinle H., Golombek S., Hann L., Schlensak C., Wendel H.P., Avci-Adali M. Blood-Contacting Biomaterials: In Vitro Evaluation of the Hemocompatibility. Front Bioeng Biotechnol. 2018; 6: 99.

Development and achievements of the scientific school «Scientific Fundamentals of Plant Materials Chemistry and Technology»

Rubtsova S.A., Chukicheva I.Yu., Hurshkainen T.V., Udoratina E.V., Kutchin A.V.
Institute of Chemistry of Komi Science Centre of the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Syktyvkar, Russia, rubtsova-sa@mail.ru

Keywords: scientific school, achievements, natural substances, complex technology, biologically active substances, plant polymers, sorption materials, pheromones, pharmacological substances.

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17341326

The Institute of Chemistry has a scientific school called «Scientific Fundamentals of Plant Materials Chemistry and Technology» under the leadership of Academician of the Russian Academy of Sciences A.V. Kutchin. In 2024, the school celebrated its 30th anniversary.

The main areas of activity of the scientific school: science foundations of resource-saving and environmentally friendly application of plant raw materials and their components for chemical products and materials production, obtaining new materials and substances creation on the base of plant polymers, fundamental problems of physiologically active compounds production on the basis of natural substances.

The report will present modern development trends and achievements in the complex processing of plant raw materials to obtain new biologically active substances and materials with valuable practical properties and a wide range of purposes.

A technology for the complex processing of coniferous wood greenery has been developed and implemented to obtain natural highly active preparations for agriculture, veterinary medicine and pharmacology. The new technology is based on the emulsion extraction method. Its advantage over traditional ones based on raw material extraction with organic solvents is an increase in the utilization rate of natural compounds, high resource-saving efficiency and environmental safety.

Methods have been developed for obtaining the main components of preparations for monitoring and combating dangerous pests of coniferous forests (bark beetles, bark beetles and longhorn beetles) based on substances of natural origin - aggregation and sex pheromones of these pests.

Innovative pharmaceutical substances based on natural compounds have been developed for the treatment of socially significant diseases. A full cycle of preclinical studies has been conducted. Technological regulations and a dosage form have been developed.

Methods have been developed for obtaining sorption materials for cleaning and restoring natural objects (water bodies, soil covers) from oil pollution, heavy metal ions and other pollutants of anthropogenic origin based on large-tonnage waste from the production and processing of wood.

Acknowledgements. This research was financially supported by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Russian Federation (State Assignments, Reg. No. 125020301261-5, 125020501549-2).

Antifungal effect of silver-containing bionanomaterials based on humic ligands

Shunkova D.M.¹, Pilguk G.¹, Tagirov T.R.¹, Karpova M.R.¹, Zykova M.V.¹

¹Siberian State Medical University, Tomsk, Russia, shunkova.dm@ssmu.ru

Keywords: humic substances; silver nanoparticles; antifungal activity; *Candida*; biofilm formation
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17341388

In 2022, the World Health Organization published a list of fungal priority pathogens. It included 19 fungal species, four of which are *Candida* fungi. They interested us due to their wide distribution area, high virulence, and the increase in cases of drug-resistant candidiasis. There is a need for new antifungal drugs that can fight these pathogens. Bionanomaterials made from natural humic substances and silver nanoparticles can become such. The goal of the study is to research the antifungal effect of silver-containing bionanomaterials based on humic ligands.

The study used clinical strains of *Candida* fungi, which were isolated in the bacteriological laboratory of the clinics of the Siberian State Medical University from various materials from patients: two strains of *C. albicans* from sputum, one strain of *C. albicans* from discharge from a surgical wound, one strain of *Candida* spp. from sputum and three strains of *Candida* spp. from urine. To study the potential antifungal effect, samples of silver-containing bionanomaterials based on humic ligands were taken, which were synthesized in the Laboratory of Natural Humic Systems of the Department of Chemistry, Lomonosov Moscow State University. We used two samples of bionanomaterials synthesized by thermal (CHP-AgNPs-kt) and microwave (CHP-AgNPs-mw) methods based on a common ligand – a matrix of humic acids from brown coal CHP (“Powhumus”, Humintech Ltd.), according to the method described in [1]. To clarify the role of humic substances in the antifungal effect of bionanomaterials, two samples of humic substances were studied from brown coal – CHP (“Powhumus”, Humintech Ltd.) and CHGen (Genesis LLC). We selected strains of *Candida* fungi capable of forming biofilms. Then, the studied substances were screened for antifungal properties. The effect of the samples on the formed biofilms was assessed. We also assessed the viability of fungi in biofilms after exposure to the studied substances.

Seven strains of *Candida* fungi capable of forming biofilms were selected. According to the screening results, the best was the bionanomaterial CHP-AgNPs-mw, which suppressed the growth of all the studied strains. It was able to destroy the biofilms of four of the seven studied strains (two strains of *C. albicans* from sputum, the strain of *C. albicans* from discharge from a surgical wound, one strain of *Candida* spp. from urine). At the same time, the humic substance sample CHGen also demonstrated antifungal properties, suppressing the growth of three strains out of seven (two strains of *C. albicans* from sputum, the strain of *C. albicans* from discharge from a surgical wound) and destroying the biofilm of the strain of *Candida* spp. from sputum. Evaluation of the viability of fungi in biofilms after exposure showed the destruction of the biofilm structure and the death of cells inside it.

Silver-containing bionanomaterials based on humic ligands exhibit antifungal properties and destroy formed fungal biofilms. In this regard, they are promising substances for the development of antifungal drugs.

This research was funded by the Russian Science Foundation, No. 20-65-47052.

References.

1. Zykova M.V., Karpova M.R., Zhang Yu, Chubik M.V., Shunkova D.M., Azarkina L.A., Mihalyov D.A., Konstantinov A.I., Plotnikov E.V., Pestryakov A.N., Perminova I.V., Belousov M.V. The Influence of Silver-Containing Bionanomaterials Based on Humic Ligands on Biofilm Formation in Opportunistic Pathogens // *Nanomaterials* 2024, 14, 1453.

Synthesis of iron(III)-humic substances complexes of different lipophilicity profile with a use of alcohol precipitation

Ushakova K.A.¹, Badun G.A.¹, Chernysheva M.G.¹, Farsobina O.A.², Zhirkova A.M.¹, Perminova I.V.¹

Lomonosov Moscow State University, Department of Chemistry, Leninskie Gory 1-3, 119991, Moscow, Russia, karina.ushakova@chemistry.msu.ru

Lomonosov Moscow State University, Department of Material Science, Leninskie Gory 1-73, 119991, Moscow, Russia

Keywords: Humic substances, Fe(III) complexes, alcohol precipitation, lipophilicity; tritium labeling
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17341475

Humic substances (HS) are supramolecular macroligands rich in functional groups that complex metal ions, enabling sustainable and biomedical applications, including iron formulations for treating iron deficiency anemia and plant chlorosis. Its hydrophilic-lipophilic balance governs membrane transport and bioavailability, tritium labeling permits molecular-level evaluation of HS behavior and lipophilicity. The aim of this work was to obtain Fe(III) complexes with humic macroligands possessing different lipophilicity profiles and to determine the effect of the alcohol precipitation on the properties of the preparations.

Sodium humate from leonardite (Powhumus 85%, Humintech Ltd, Germany) was used as a HS. The tritium label was introduced into HS by the method of thermal activation of tritium. Anhydrous FeCl₃ (UD-Bio, China) served as the iron precursor. The synthesis was carried out in two stages: precipitation of Fe(OH)₃ at 7-10 °C and pH = 7, and addition of the resulting precipitate to HS at 60 °C in an alkaline medium (pH = 11), followed by acidification to pH = 6.5. The resulting preparations were subjected to multiple alcohol precipitation with ethanol with an increasing proportion of the organic phase (30 – 70 %). A control sample was obtained without alcohol precipitation. 7 samples were obtained in total. Lipophilicity was determined by the octanol-water partition coefficient (K_{ow}) using liquid scintillation spectrometry, and particle core sizes was determined by transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and the hydrodynamic radius was determined by dynamic light scattering (DLS). Lipophilicity was assessed in two series: with pre-centrifugation (removal of the solid phase) and without. Centrifugation before alcohol precipitation decreased lipophilicity ($K_{ow} = 0.11 - 0.24$), whereas increasing the ethanol content in the non-centrifuged series raised K_{ow} to 0.63 - 0.65; the control samples showed moderate lipophilicity ($K_{ow} = 0.27 - 0.40$). Concomitantly, water solubility increased from 57 g/L in the control to 120 - 145 g/L in precipitated samples. These results indicate that alcohol precipitation drives the solubility gain irrespective of pre-centrifugation, while the pre-centrifugation step primarily modulates lipophilicity-lowering K_{ow} when applied, and yielding higher K_{ow} when omitted-thus providing a handle to tune the hydrophilic-lipophilic balance. According to TEM, the iron-oxide core size decreased from 6 nm to 1 - 3 nm after precipitation. DLS showed that the hydrodynamic radius of precipitated samples increased with ethanol content from 24.3 ± 4.0 nm to 38.4 ± 3.6 nm. The control sample exhibited the largest mean hydrodynamic radius (60.7 ± 6.2 nm). Alcohol precipitation yields Fe(III) - HS nanoparticles with smaller inorganic cores and more compact, less polydisperse hydrodynamic ensembles than the non-precipitated control.

Thus, the method makes it possible to regulate the key characteristics of Fe(III) - HS complexes: lipophilicity, solubility, and particle size. Controlling these parameters at the synthesis stage opens up opportunities for the development of effective and safe iron-based preparations.

Acknowledgements. The work was carried out within the framework of the State Task 122040600057-3.

Humic substances-assisted immobilization of magnetite onto sawdust increases surface area and copper bonding of the sorbent

Zhirkova A.M., Lakienco G.P., Kriuchkova D.S., Gadzhibagomedov R.A., Rajabzoda P.A., Perminova I.V.

Lomonosov Moscow State University, Moscow, Russia, Zhirkova_am@mail.ru

Keywords: humic substances, copper, sorption, BET, magnetite.
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17343321

Pollution of water bodies with heavy metals due to anthropogenic activities, in particular metallurgical production, is one of the most acute environmental problems. Heavy metals are highly toxic, prone to bioaccumulation and long-term preservation in aquatic ecosystems, which leads to disruption of biogeochemical cycles and degradation of biodiversity. In this regard, the development of efficient and cost-effective sorbents for the remediation of heavy metal pollution remains a pressing issue.

We synthesized magnetite immobilized on sawdust under two conditions: with and without humic substances. The procedure involved mixing Fe(II)/Fe(III) salts with sawdust, precipitating magnetite in ammoniacal medium, and isolating the products by filtration and drying.

We investigated the specific surface area of the humate-containing sorbent and the effect on the ability of sorbents to adsorb copper from natural waters, comparing it with the sorbent obtained without humate and raw sawdust. The sorbents were characterized using various physico-chemical methods. X-ray phase analysis and Mossbauer spectroscopy confirmed the predominance of the magnetite phase in the synthesized materials. The Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) specific surface area (SSA) was determined from the linear plot in the relative pressure range of 0.05–0.3 P/P₀. The pore size distribution was calculated in the relative pressure range (P/P₀) from 0.1 to 0.99 using the Barrett–Joyner–Halenda (BJH) method. The results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Surface characteristics and sorption properties of sawdust-based sorbents

Samples	SD	SD-Fe	SD-Fe-HS
BET Surface Area, m ² /g	12.5	5.3	45.7
Cumulative Pore Volume, ml/g	0.013	0.022	0.074
Average Pore Diameter, nm	3.5	12.9	5.8
Maximum equilibrium adsorption capacity, mg/g.	3.8	7.1	7.8

Modification with Fe₃O₄ reduced the surface area of sawdust, but increased the average pore diameter, indicating the formation of larger pores. The addition of humic substances together with Fe₃O₄ markedly enhanced both surface area and pore volume, which directly correlated with the highest sorption capacity (7.8 mg/g) observed for SD-Fe-HS. These results demonstrate the potential of humic-substance–modified magnetic sorbents as an accessible and efficient tool for the removal of heavy metals from contaminated waters contributing to the mitigation of ecological risks associated with industrial pollution.

Acknowledgements. This research was carried out within the framework of the state task “Ecology” (CITIS no. 122040600057-3). This work was supported in part by M.V. Lomonosov Moscow State University Program of Development.

Effect of C-based soil conditioners on the composition and properties of soil organic matter

Zhurba V.S.¹, Yakimenko O.S.¹

¹Lomonosov Moscow State University, Department of Soil Science, Moscow, Russia
zhurbaviktoria@mail.ru

Keywords: biochar, commercial humate, labile C pool
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17343416

Biochar is a carbon-containing product of the thermal decomposition of organic raw materials under conditions of limited oxygen access and is widely regarded as a sustainable soil conditioner capable of improving the physical and chemical characteristics of agroecosystems [1]. One of the key areas of research into its impact is its effect on the chemical properties of soils, including humic substance content. Humic substances are natural high-molecular organic compounds formed as a result of the transformation of plant and microbial residues in the soil. They form the basis of humus and play a key role in soil fertility.

The aim of the study was to investigate the effect of two types of biochar, separately and in combination with a humic preparation, on the chemical properties of sod-podzolic soil in a series of model experiments and to identify their potential as soil conditioners.

The application of soil conditioners contributed to an increase in the carbon and nitrogen content of the soil. In the control, the carbon content was 1.42%, with the addition of biochar from siderites – 2.02%, biochar from coffee – 2.22%, potassium humate – 1.8%. Total nitrogen also increased, with the maximum value (0.17%) observed when using biochar from coffee.

Water-soluble carbon in the control was 186.1 mg/kg. The highest values were recorded when potassium humate was applied (379.9 mg/kg), while biochar exhibited sorption properties, reducing or retaining mobile forms. A similar pattern was observed for nitrogen: in the control — 46.94 mg/kg, with the addition of potassium humate — 57.66 mg/kg, with biochar from coffee — 49.41 mg/kg, with biochar from green manure — a decrease to 44.28 mg/kg.

Alkali-hydrolysable forms also increased significantly with the addition of potassium humate (carbon — up to 3917.0 mg/kg, nitrogen — up to 286.2 mg/kg). Mixtures of biochar with humate showed intermediate values, indicating the sorption capacity of biochar and the leading role of humate as a source of humic substances.

The total C content increases by 0.4-0.8% in accordance with the amount of organic soil conditioners added. Neither biochar affects the size of the mobile pool C in both aqueous and alkaline extracts, whereas humate, separately and in mixture with biochar, increases the proportion of mobile fractions of soil organic matter from 10 to 20-30% to total C. Under the conditions of this experiment, the organic matter of biochar did not transform and remained in the non-hydrolysable part of humus.

In the applicative phytotest on wheat seedlings, biomass growth of the test culture was detected only in the variants with biochar from coffee and humate, amounting to 4-9% compared to the control, but the differences are not significant. A decrease in biomass was observed in the variants with the addition of biochar from green manure and a mixture of coffee biochar with humate (up to 62-75% compared to the control, statistically insignificant) and a mixture of green manure biochar with humate (up to 65% compared to the control, statistically significant).

Reference

1. Weber, Kathrin, and Peter Quicker. "Properties of biochar." *Fuel* 217 (2018): 240-261.

4. The role of humic substances and plant biopolymers in the context of the bioeconomy

Biospheric functions of humic substances – geochemical barriers and nature-like technologies

Dinu M.¹

¹Vernadsky Institute of Geochemistry and Analytical Chemistry, Moscow, Russia

Keywords: humic substances of natural waters, inactivation of metal ions and other substances, autochthonous and allochthonous organic substances
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17343465

A key function of humic substances is their ability to reduce the migration of toxic water components. Lake waters and soil waters in the protected area of the Novgorod Region contain varying proportions of natural organic matter, and, accordingly, geochemical barriers also vary in their retention strength.

The concentration of allochthonous organic matter (flows from the catchment area) and autochthonous organic matter (formed within the reservoir) in lake waters varies depending on temperature, which affects the balance of accessible and labile metal species.

The greatest influence of autochthonous organic matter on metal formation, over a time scale, is characteristic of the alkaline Lake Valdaiskoye in virtually all periods. This influence is greatest during the growing season (summer) and the period of maximum phytoplankton destruction (fall) and the release of organic matter. In summer, 70% of the total organic matter in the water is autochthonous, and in autumn, up to 60%. The contribution of autochthonous matter to metal complexation in waters from lysimetric ponds located near the city is somewhat lower. The main metals associated with such organic compounds are copper, zinc,

The waters of the acidified Lake Gusinoe are characterized by a dominant content of humic acids in organic matter (up to 90%, even in summer); the most stable complex compounds are formed with iron, aluminum, copper, and nickel ions. Lysimetric waters in the forest zone in spring and summer contain up to 40% complex compounds of metals with lower molecular weight organic matter. As in the corresponding lake, cationic compounds with humic polymers predominate.

Changes in zeta potential directly depend on the balance of allochthonous and autochthonous components. Lysimetric waters of the humus horizon in forests, with very low pH and zero alkalinity, generate a significant electrochemically negative potential, characteristic of stable organic colloids, primarily of humic origin. An increase in the content of autochthonous organic matter shifts this potential toward zero and positive values, so not all ratios of allochthonous and autochthonous substances in natural waters are thermodynamically stable.

Funding: This work was supported by grant R24-27-00144. "Biogeochemical migration of carbon and substances in natural waters: the Arctic and European territory of Russia."

New methods of chemical functionalization of peat

Efanov M.V.¹, Konshin V.V.²

¹LLC "MIP "Yugra – Biotechnology", Khanty-Mansiysk, Russia, efanov_1973@mail.ru

²Altay state technical university, Barnaul, Russia

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17343516

Peat is a unique natural composite, a source of humic substances and raw materials for industry and agriculture. The aim of this work is to develop a new carboxymethyl derivatives from peat to study the possibility of its application in the industry oil and gas production [1]. The influence of duration mechanochemical treatment of peat on the process of carboxymethylation under the action of natrium monochloroacetic salt in the presence of NaOH, the temperature of the alkylation – 25 °C (tabl. 1) [2]. The influence of duration mechanochemical treatment of peat on the process of benzylation under the action of benzyl chloride in the presence of NaOH (tabl. 1) [2]. The chemical composition of products of benzylation of peat given in the table 2.

Table 1. The influence of the molar ratio of OH:NaOH:m-ClAcNa in the carboxymethylation of peat in conditions of intensive mechanical grinding on the properties of the obtained products

Sample	Duration carboxymethylation of peat, min	Content of carboxymethyl groups, %	Solubility in water, %
Peat	-	-	5
1	10	17.9	42
2	20	20.5	69
3	30	20.7	71
4	60	24.7	76

It was found that with an increase in the molar ratio there is an increase in the content of bound carboxymethyl groups in products and their solubility in water (tabl. 1).

Table 2. Benzylation of peat

Duration benzylation of peat, min	Content of benzyl groups, %	Solubility in chloroform, %
10	3.8	17
20	4.7	25
30	5.9	36
40	6.8	45
50	7.7	53
60	8.6	60

It is shown that the increase in the duration benzylation of peat is the increase in the content and solubility products in chloroform (tabl. 2).

References

1. Efanov M.V., Yagovitin D.V. Method carboxymethylation of peat // Patent of Russian Federation № 2656461. Published 05.06.2018. Bulletin № 16.
2. Efanov M.V., Sartakov M.P., Konshin V.V. Benzylation of peat mechanochemical method // Chemistry of natural compounds, 2020. № 5. P. 840-842.

The use of LLC Lignohumat preparations containing humic substances in agriculture

Kondratiev V.M.

Lignohumat LLC, Saint Petersburg, Russia, vk@lignohumate.ru

Keywords: spring wheat, herbicidal stress, yield, lignohumate

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17343561

The intensive nature of agricultural activity involves the use of a larger number of chemicals – mineral fertilizers, pesticides (herbicides, insecticides, fungicides). Herbicides have the greatest phytotoxicity for cultivated plants. An indirect way to assess the herbicide load is the volume of herbicide production. In Russia, from 2016 to 2022, the volume of herbicide production increased from 49.9 to 126.0 thousand tons [1], which indicates a 2.5-fold increase in the herbicide burden on agricultural crops. Such growth leads to inhibition of the metabolism of agricultural plants, inhibition of development. In this regard, there is a need to remove plants from the "herbicide pit". One of the ways to overcome herbicidal stress is the use of preparations containing humic substances. Due to the large number of functional groups, humic substances have a number of properties, one of which is the formation of complexes with molecules of the active substance of herbicides [2]. The most technologically advanced method of obtaining humic substances is the processing of lignin-containing plant raw materials obtained during wood processing. NPO RET LLC has developed and successfully uses a waste-free technology for processing plant raw materials (lignosulfonate) by the method of oxidative-hydrolytic degradation, which makes it possible to obtain high-quality liquid and powdered humic preparations sold by LIGNOHUMAT LLC.

The preparations of LIGNOHUMAT LLC are annually tested in the fields of agricultural producers, where they are used together in tank mixtures with pesticides. The accounting of yields in the tests was carried out according to generally accepted methods. The obtained yield data was mathematically processed by the method of variance analysis. In 2021, the tests were carried out on crops of spring wheat of the Ekada variety on the farm of Ural-Tau Agricultural Enterprise LLC. During the growing season, foliar treatment was carried out, according to the technology of the farm, with the herbicide Trisil (Tifensulfuron-methyl 300 g/kg+Tribenuron-methyl 300 g/kg+Florasulam 100 g/kg). In the experimental version, the preparation Lignohumate BM was added to the tank mixture at a dose of 1 l/ha. The yield in the control variant was 20.5 c/ha, in the experimental variant – 22.7 c/ha (HCP0.05 = 1.1 c/ha). In 2023, tests were carried out in the fields of CJSC Plemzavod Yubileyny on spring wheat of the Licamero variety. During the growing season, foliar treatments were carried out with the following pesticides, according to the technology of the farm: Absolute+Tribune SP, Zeppelin CE+Title 390+AgroPrim ME. In the experimental version, Argolan Aqua was added to the tank mixture at a dose of 0.5 l/ha. The yield in the control variant was 35.2 c/ha, in the experimental variant – 39.0 c/ha (HCP0.05 = 1.8 c/ha). An increase in the yield of spring wheat by 2.2 and 3.8 c/ha, respectively, compared with the control, indicates the overcoming of herbicidal stress.

Based on the results of the tests, it can be concluded that the humic substances contained in Lignohumate preparations have a stimulating effect and make it possible for cultivated plants to overcome herbicidal stress, but the issue of the mutual influence of herbicides and humic substances on weeds remains unclear.

References

1. Agriculture in Russia: [electronic resource]. URL: https://rosstat.gov.ru/storage/mediabank/S_x_2023.pdf (date of reference: 08/01/2025).
2. Popov A. I. Humic substances: properties, structure, formation. St. Petersburg: Publishing House of St. Petersburg University, 2004. 248 p.

The principle of cascade utilization in the processing of coffee silverskin

Martynov V.V.¹, Shchemelinina T.N.¹, Anchugova E.M.¹, Perestoronniy D.V.², Molodkina N.R.²

¹Institute of Biology, FIC Komi Sci. Centre Ur. Br. RAS, Syktyvkar, Russia, martynov.v.v@ib.komisc.ru

²ITMO University, Saint Petersburg, Russia

Keywords: waste, coffee silverskin, cascade utilization, biocomposite

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17343641

The cascade utilization involves the sequential multi-stage processing of a bioresource to extract target components at each stage. Coffee silverskin (CS), a lignocellulosic waste product from coffee roasting [1], was used as a carbon source for cultivating the xylophilic basidiomycete *Trametes* sp., an enzyme producer. Following filtration and enzyme purification, the process yielded two main by-products: spent medium (SM), which contains a complex of micro- and macroelements (Table) and is suitable for recycling, and biomass (approx. 5%) consisting of mycelium and residual CS.

Table. Composition of the initial nutrient medium and spent medium

Sample	N-NH ₄ ⁺	SO ₄ ²⁻	PO ₄ ³⁻	mg/dm ³				μg/dm ³	
				F ⁻	Ca	Mg	K	Zn	Al
INM*	62±12	1440	540	0,84±0,21	31±5	52±8	250±40	1150±230	19±6
SM	47±9	960±120	420±80	0,53±0,13	30±5	41±6	200±30	780±160	11±4

*Note: INM – initial nutrient medium

Figure. Appearance of the mycelium-based biocomposite

Sawdust and CS-based lignocellulosic substrate ensured effective mycelial colonization, as confirmed by complete surface coverage and dense internal growth of the biocomposite (Figure). The biocomposite exhibited high hygroscopicity due to its porous structure and the hydrophilic properties of the chitin-glucan complex. The material retained its structural integrity, and subsequent drying demonstrated resistance to cyclic moisture exposure. The density of the biocomposite was found to depend on the substrate composition and processing methods; pressed fine-disperse substrates achieved a density of 0.022–0.030 g/cm³, comparable to expanded polystyrene, which makes them promising for use in lightweight structures.

Thus, the cascade utilization of CS contributes to waste reduction, a minimized environmental footprint, enhanced economic efficiency of bioresource use, as well as job creation and strengthened energy security.

This work was supported by the State Assignment of the IB FRC Komi SC UB RAS, (No. 125021201993-3, “Microbial Communities of Northern Ecosystems, their Biotechnological Potential and Technologies for its Realization”).

References

1. Biorefinery potential of coffee silverskin: Composition and applications / E. M. Anchugova, E. V. Udoratina, E. G. Kazakova, A. O. Nosova, M. V. Uspenskaya, T. N. Shchemelinina // IJROWA. – 2024. – Vol. 13. – № 5. DOI: 10.57647/ijrowa-b5y0-qf23

Evolutionary chemistry of carbon as a molecular basis for ecoadaptive technologies

Perminova I.V.

Lomonosov Moscow State University, Department of Chemistry, Leninskie gory 1-3, 119991 Moscow, Russia, iperminova@gmail.com

Keywords: humic systems, evolutionary chemistry, high resolution mass spectrometry, artificial humification, ecoadaptive technology
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17343694

Organic matter on Earth is involved in continuous processes of de novo synthesis and decay, which at the global level correspond to photosynthesis and humification comprising the global ecosystem metabolism. Humic systems play the role of ecosystem metabolome and bear the molecular imprint of climatic, geological and geographical conditions as well as the influence of anthropogenic activity. The study and systematization of the molecular composition of humic systems is an essential prerequisite for ecosystem metabolomics aimed at molecular diagnostics of global processes of organic matter transformation. The optimal way to solve this problem is to use Fourier transform ion cyclotron resonance mass spectrometry (FTICR MS), which has an extremely high resolution and distinguishes millions of carbon atoms with different chemical environments in humic systems. We report here about the developed a highly efficient algorithm for analyzing information-rich mass spectra for humic systems - total mass difference algorithm (TMDS), which formed the basis of many software.

An important problem of geoecology is the restoration of life support functions of polluted and disturbed ecosystems as a result of anthropogenic impact. Humic systems play a key role in self-purification, self-organization and self-healing of contaminated ecosystems. Therefore, a very urgent problem is the reproduction of these natural mechanisms in chemicals, materials and processes for development of ecoadaptive technologies for remediation of disturbed environments. The prospects of this area are confirmed by the results of our many years of research. Few examples will be given in this report. For the first time, it is proposed to use solid stabilizers to create a new generation of dispersants and washing agents based on Pickering emulsions for cleaning oil-contaminated media. This approach was used for in situ technology for cleaning soils from diesel fuel pollution using humic-bentonite compounds, designed to clean contaminated soils in the Norilsk area. The knowledge gained can be used for solving other geological problems. Currently we imply accelerated in situ humification for remediation of sludge lignin dumpsite at the Baykal lake located at the former Baykal Paper Mill facilities. The aim of our efforts is to achieve dewatering and oxidative polymerization of lignin which will provide mechanically stable and fertile grounds for plants.

Thus implication of molecular chemistry of humic systems evolution may contribute to solving organic waste problem which is one of the main task for the circle economy and contribute for targeted application of ecoadaptive technologies.

The work was supported by the State Budgetary Task 102-25 (0604).

Advertisement

ЛИГНОГУМАТ

КОНЦЕНТРИРОВАННЫЙ ГУМИНОВЫЙ ПРЕПАРАТ

The «LIGNOHUMATE» company manufactures and put up for sale growth stimulants, fertilizers and feed additives under Lignohumate and L-Green brands. The products are manufactured at our own plant using a patented technology that ensures strong automated quality control, complete solubility and a high concentration of the active substance - up to 900 g/kg of biologically active components of organic origin.

Ecologically friendly products

Most of the products are certified for organic farming, which confirms their ecological cleanness and wide range of application. Our agronomical service experts with years of experience are ready to provide free consultations on the product use on various crops.

Free expert consultations

Our agronomical service with years of experience is ready to help in the selecting and application of products for various crops.

International appreciation

According to the company's sales statistics, the products are used annually on an area of about 15 million hectares. Distribution is established in all agricultural regions of Russia, as well as abroad. The products are exported to the CIS and countries of the near and far abroad: Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Turkey, China, Serbia. At the moment, Lignohumate has proven its effectiveness and is successfully sold in more than 25 countries around the world.

Successful partnership

We are pleased to offer potential partners three ways of beneficial cooperation:

- direct supplies of preparations to agricultural holdings and farms;
- distribution partnership;
- development of exclusive formulations for specific needs.

We are confident that our innovative solutions will help improving results and achieving high yields and product quality.

Follow the news and updates on our official website lignohumate.ru. For any questions, please contact us by email at info@lignohumate.ru or by phone at **8 (800) 555-75-72**.

Life Force Group: Инновационные решения на основе гуминовых веществ для сельского хозяйства и здоровья человека

Life Force Group – международная группа компаний, объединяющая исследовательский центр и современные производственные предприятия, специализирующиеся на разработке и производстве продукции на основе гуминовых веществ. На протяжении 24 лет компания ведет активную деятельность в области создания кормовых добавок и смесей, удобрений и средств для восстановления плодородия почв. Ключевым сырьем является леонардит, добываемый в экологически чистых регионах Сибири и характеризующийся высоким содержанием гуминовых и фульвовых кислот с уникальным спектром биологической активности.

Компания применяет собственные технологии экстракции и фракционирования гуминовых веществ из леонардита, что позволяет получать высококачественную и эффективную продукцию с заданными физико-химическими свойствами. Продукция проходит строгий контроль качества и соответствует международным стандартам.

Кормовые добавки под торговой маркой Reasil® с высоким содержанием гуминовых веществ получили широкое распространение и признание в хозяйствах России и стран ближнего зарубежья. Эффективность Reasil® обусловлена положительным влиянием на физиологические процессы организма животных, что проявляется в повышении рентабельности и продуктивности, улучшении качественных показателей продукции, укреплении иммунитета и обеспечении ее ветеринарной безопасности.

В настоящее время компания активно внедряет в практику микроэлементные комплексы Life Force® на основе органической матрицы, обеспечивающие высокую биодоступность микроэлементов и оптимизацию минерального питания сельскохозяйственных животных и растений, а также повышение их устойчивости к стрессовым факторам.

Life Force Group не останавливается на достигнутом и ведет постоянный поиск новых эффективных решений, направленных на улучшение здоровья и продуктивности растений и животных, а также на повышение качества жизни человека. В рамках этой стратегии в компании создано новое направление по производству пищевых добавок на основе гуминовых кислот, предназначенных для естественной нормализации и поддержания баланса метаболических процессов, улучшения антиоксидантного статуса и укрепления иммунной системы.

Life Force Group уделяет особое внимание научным исследованиям и сотрудничает с ведущими научно-исследовательскими институтами и университетами. Компания стремится внести вклад в развитие знаний о гуминовых веществах и их роли в обеспечении устойчивого развития сельского хозяйства и улучшении здоровья человека.

Узнайте больше о компании: <https://lifeforce.pro/>

Научное издание

Tenth International Conference of the CIS IHSS
on Humic Innovative Technologies

Humic substances and plant raw materials in the context of a closed-loop economy

Book of abstracts

Оригинал-макет: Е. Лодыгин
Технический редактор: Л. Огородовая

Электронное издание

Подписано в печать 01.10.25. Усл. печ. л. 4.8.
Заказ 08(25).

Институт биологии Коми научного центра
Уральского отделения Российской академии наук
167982, Россия, Республика Коми,
г. Сыктывкар, ул. Коммунистическая, 28

The conference is held with the financial support of the following organizations:

Sponsor of the conference:

ЛИГНОГУМАТ
КОНЦЕНТРИРОВАННЫЙ ГУМИНОВЫЙ ПРЕПАРАТ

Lignohumat LLC, St.
Petersburg, Russia
<http://www.lignohumate.com>

Life Force
— GROUP —

Life Force Group, Moscow,
Russia <https://lifeforce.pro/>